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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SPATRA project aims to enhance land transport monitoring and management through development and implementation of two innovative applications based on usage of satellite data. The project commenced on 01.01.2024 and spans over 24 months, with OHB Digital Services as the lead beneficiary.

Satellite data has revolutionised data collection across various sectors, providing invaluable benefits to scientific research and enhancing tracking and monitoring capabilities. However, there remains untapped potential for using satellite technology in smaller-scale tracking operations such as transport operation. By developing two downstream applications for rail and road transport, the SPATRA project represents a significant step forward in the application of space-based technologies for transport monitoring and management with the potential to influence policy, legislation, and market acceptance in the transport sector.

This deliverable D2.1 provides a first step towards the noted project goals. D2.1 focuses on requirements and specifications for two use-cases, road and rail transport. It provides a comprehensive overview of the methodologies and approaches adopted by the project Consortium, along with the key findings and future actions to be conducted to achieve the project objectives. The document provides a comprehensive analysis of the user needs and challenges for the considered use-cases in the road and rail transport monitoring and management, based on the inputs from the main stakeholders and end-users Nelt (road transport use-case) and Serbian Railways Infrastructure (rail transport use-case). The deliverable D2.1 document also defines the functional and non-functional requirements, system specifications (both hardware and software), data sources and processing steps, the preliminary system architectures and components, and the interfaces and integration roadmaps for the two use-cases/pilots – road and rail. The deliverable D2.1 aims to establish a clear understanding of the end-user requirements and the system specifications necessary to guide the development of the SPATRA project's road and rail transport monitoring and management solutions based on using the satellite data.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS, ACRONYMS AND DEFINITIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Definition
AOI	Area of Interest
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CEP	Circular Error Probable
CDSE	Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
COG	Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF
CRT	Critical Rail Temperature
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
EGNOS	E uropean G eostationary O verlay S ervice
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
FoI	Feature(s) of Interest
(G)UI	(Graphical) User Interface
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
LIDAR	L <i>igh</i> t D <i>etect</i> ion and R <i>ang</i> ing
LST	Land Surface Temperature
MSG	Meteosat Second Generation
MTG	Meteosat Third Generation
MVC	Model-View-Controller
M2M	Machine-To-Machine
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
PoI	Point(s) of Interest
REST	REpresentational State Transfer (protocol)
RDP	Road Infrastructure Monitoring Pilot Use Case
RTT	Rail Track Temperature
RTBR	Rail Track Buckling Risk
RWP	RailWay monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings Pilot use case
SBAS	S atellite- B ased A ugmentation S ystem
SR	System Requirement
STAC	Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UX	User Experience
UN	User Need
UR	User Requirement

UC	Use Case
VRT	Virtual Raster
ICT	Information & Communication Technology

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Document purpose

This deliverable document D2.1 reports the activities, effort and work undertaken in Work Package 2 (WP2- Requirements and specifications) of SPATRA project, and specifically the results of tasks T2.1-Define SPATRA functional and non-functional requirements, T2.2-Develop use case specification, and T2.3-Devise a component specification and integration roadmap. Two pilot use-cases for land transport, road and rail, monitoring and management have been defined and appropriate requirements collected, including requirements from the two pilots end-users – logistic company Nelt and Serbian Railways Infrastructure.

Requirements Analysis Approach

SPATRA Consortium followed a bottom-up approach. As first, the user needs and user requirements were collected using three different channels: online interview, questionnaire and onsite Workshop. Starting from the analysis of the functional and non-functional requirements from the user needs, definitions of the pilots and the information flows, external and internal data sources, generic data types, acquisition/computation periods and frequencies, as well as analysis of the satellite-data spatial resolution were conducted.

A unified methodological approach, applicable to both considered use-cases of land transport, for classifying pertinent system requirements for the project's later phases (concept/specification & implementation phase) was adopted and followed. The adopted approach is considered to enhance the project's overall workflow for several reasons:

- It enables examination of different factors that affect the design and implementation of the system components. By separating the requirements into functional and non-functional, it eases the process of finding and ranking specific user needs.
- It enables all project stakeholders to understand the requirements, and so to work together for a common goal. The use of a consistent language and framework for definition of requirements enables avoiding of misunderstandings and errors, leading to an efficient and effective project delivery.
- The classification of requirements to functional and non-functional facilitates a more effective comparison of different transport monitoring solutions. By evaluating different options using the same criteria, it becomes simpler to recognize each solution's pros and cons and make informed choices about which solution is the best aligned with the project goals and desired outcomes.
- The requirements were prioritised based on the following approach:
 - SHALL - indicates a mandatory requirement,
 - SHOULD - indicates a recommendable requirement,
 - MAY - used to indicate non-mandatory requirements that are nice-to-have, but not crucial for successful system operation.

1.2 Document structure

The document is outlined as follows:

- **Chapter 2** provides the results of collecting the end-user needs, analysing the use-cases, and defining the end-user requirements (Task 2.1). One of the end-users of intended SPATRA satellite-based pilots, logistic company Nelt, is a project partner, and the other end-user, Serbian Railway Infrastructure is an active advisory board member. Both end-users were actively involved in definition of the end-user needs, requirements and problems encountered by the users in transport monitoring. Starting from this, the analysis of both end-user requirements to define SPATRA systems requirements for two applications in road and rail transport monitoring was conducted. The report on performed analysis is given in this Chapter 2.
- **Chapter 3** covers two use-cases, road and rail, technical developments specifications (Task 2.2): assessment of appropriate hardware configurations and software systems components, storage capacities, technology providers, data availability, technical risks, and standards. The Chapter also covers initial high-level system architecture designs of both pilots, including processing workflows and main technical decisions, as well as continuous integration and deployment strategies and graphical user interface (GUI) mock-ups describing user interactions. Chapter 3 also covers the specification of components which enable interoperability of the SPATRA pilot systems (Task 2.3). The specification of interfaces, which provide possibility to integrate with third party systems is given, as well as a roadmap as a basis of the plan for field-test validation of both SPATRA pilot systems.

Preliminary considerations of different data to be used in both pilot systems with the focus on satellite data, as well as preliminary consideration of data processing and data fusion methods is given in Chapter 3 as well. In section 3.2.2.2, for the railway pilot system-estimation of the rail track temperature using satellite data, it is described that data fusion approaches will be used in the thermal downscaling and the rail track temperature (RTT) prediction. In the road pilot case, fusion of the most intensely acquired and demanding high-resolution spatiotemporal real-time data is planned to be supported mainly and optimally at the points of practical acquisition – on the processing companion boards of the surveillance UAVs, as specified in section 3.1.2.1.2. Used data will be finally described in detail in deliverable D3.1 (Month 14), and the data processing methods for road and rail pilot systems will be described in detail in deliverables D3.2 (Month 20) and D3.2 (Month 20) respectively.

2 END-USER REQUIREMENTS AND USE CASES ANALYSIS

2.1 Road Infrastructure Monitoring Pilot Use Case (RDP)

2.1.1 RDP use case description

Cross-border road congestion (Figure 1) is a problem that occurs when traffic flow at international borders becomes excessive, causing delays and disruptions in road transportation. This is an essential problem in non-EU countries, where the congestion on the border could be caused by a combination of factors such as increased trade and tourism, inadequate infrastructure, and inconsistent regulations and customs procedures.

Figure 1. An example of cross-border road congestion.

Congestion at international borders can lead to significant economic losses, as goods and passengers are delayed in reaching their destinations. This can result in increased costs for businesses, as well as reduced productivity and competitiveness. Additionally, road congestions can have a negative impact on the environment and public health, as they increase air pollution and contribute to traffic-related accidents. Further to this, according to regulations, truck drivers can drive for a certain period after which they are obliged to take a break. However, parking places are not always available, and these breaks should be planned upfront.

Overall, addressing cross-border road congestion and parking availability are critical steps in supporting economic growth and development, improving the environment, and ensuring that people and goods can move efficiently on the road and across the borders. The motivation for addressing this problem is to improve the efficiency and reliability of cross-border trade, which suffers from inefficiency for logistic companies without exception. For instance, on the “Horgoš” border crossing between Serbia and Hungary, during the summer the capacity is 400 trucks per day and the actual number in the peak goes over 1500 trucks, leaving cargo more than a few days on the border. The

SPATRA road pilot will involve Nelt², one of the leading logistics companies in Southeast Europe. The fleet of Nelt vehicles enables the realisation of over 23,000 complete loads per year, in all temperature and other transport modes.

Through faster processes, time-saving procedures, transparency and succinct administration, key objectives within the main goal of the company are to optimise logistics costs and efficiency of operations. In addition to its fleet of transport vehicles, Nelt cooperates with other carriers throughout the region. This way, Nelt can quickly organise transport to any European destination. Depending on the needs of clients, international and domestic road transport can be organised either as a direct or as a collective transport.

SPATRA satellite-based RDP services and tools would bring obvious benefits and enhancements to the end-users in the road logistics sector for the cross-border road congestion monitoring. However, one of the main issues with using solely EGNSS and Copernicus data (set out in the Project ambition as primary satellite-based non-commercial Earth Observation (EO) services to be exploited) remains that with two near-polar-orbiting satellites, the revisit time over a monitored location is approximately 5 days - which makes it impossible to do the recognition in real-time. Accordingly, the SENTINEL data can be used mainly to build longer time-series over months (years) for forecasts generation, and this prior knowledge is further to be enhanced by the on-demand real time in-situ observations and measurements using UAVs, as well as potential congestions detection with cameras in border zones.

2.1.2 RDP user needs and challenges

Table 1 below lists the user needs identified after the evaluation of the outcomes of the user stories, experiences in congestion and parking availability forecasting and management, and ideation of possible service features to be implemented, all collected and resulting from continuous consultations and communication with the end users (stakeholders from the road transport and logistics sector), as well as two workshops dedicated to this, since the start of the Project. The main consulted stakeholder and end-user was Nelt, one of the most successful business systems in the Adriatic region in the field of logistics and distribution, who is also the project partner supporting fully all SPATRA project activities. Besides Nelt, different stakeholders were consulted, such as DTS-Delta Transport Systems. Table below represents a list of consolidated user needs.

Table 1 - User needs description for RDP

ID	User Need (UN) Description	UN category
UN-101	Users need timely (preferably real-time or near-real-time) and precise information on traffic congestions and delays on border crossings and the information on widest possible adjacent or additional monitored traffic frequencies on the roads and supporting infrastructure – all events and changes detected by the monitoring and how they possibly	User Experience, Reliability, Performance, Data Analytics,

² <https://www.nelt.com/logistika/>

	affect (extend/delay/invalidate...) the ETA of each of their managed trucks or other fleet vehicles on route.	Monitoring & Traceability
UN-102	Users likewise need timely and precise information on the availability of critical supporting infrastructure assets for planning the routes and mandatory breaks along them – primarily the availability of parking places in the vicinity of border zones and identified congestion-prone areas.	User Experience, Reliability, Performance
UN-103	Additionally, and particularly in case the key timely monitoring information from UN-101 and UN-102 above is not available, users need reliable and timely predictions of the emergence and patterns of critical congestions and delays, based on the collected historical monitoring and other related data.	User Experience, Predictive Analytics, Automation, Reliability, Performance
UN-104	The key important information stated in UN-101 to UN-103 above should preferably be proactively communicated to the users through alerting and notifications, as soon as any relevant change or event is registered in monitoring, or in frequent periodicity.	User Experience, Automation, Timing Constraints
UN-105	The monitoring and predicted outputs and resulting data or notifications/alerts should be provided or exposed to the route planning users or their existing tools preferably through additional M2M communication interface (such as service APIs), to be actionable for route planning, adjustments, customised ETA calculation, or optimisation.	User Experience, Automation, Predictive Analytics
UN-106	Comprehensive reporting – the users need detailed and granular historical and ad-hoc reporting on the monitored and detected events and performed service actions, all identified and predicted congestions, delays, and their effects on the route ETAs, planning and actual execution.	Reporting, Predictive Analytics
UN-107	The reports should be possible to interactively stratify, filter and aggregate and get basic descriptive statistics per detected key events (congestions, delays), trucks and drivers, on-route features or points of interest, and vehicle telemetry and performance parameters, where available.	Interactive Analytics, Reporting
UN-108	Configurability - the key driving parameters of the needed system and service functionalities stated above – like periodic frequency of notifications/alerts from UN-103, predictions time windows from	Scalability, Interoperability,

	UN-104, or other monitoring/detection parameters that affect the UX - should preferably be configurable by the users (additionally to the default predefined parameter values).	Sustainability, User Experience
UN-109	A qualified user (in higher-privileged controlling or admin role) must be enabled to interactively report or label any specific past detected or predicted key event, or a set of events provided by the service, as potentially questionable or wrong, if the evidence from the field supports it (monitoring sensors or detection algorithms can generally malfunction or make mistakes).	User Interface, Interactive Analytics, Monitoring & Traceability
UN-110	Users should be able to enter (and subsequently edit, amend or delete) known announced or expected periods or patterns of high likelihood of congestions and delays at specific points or areas - like customs shift change periods known in advance, or administrative procedure updates or introductions announced by the relevant authorities through news or followed dedicated information sources. The ETA delay calculation and notification/alerting service modules should be informed of, and process, these registered high likelihoods of congestions.	User Interface, Interactive Analytics
UN-111	The service needs to be user-friendly, easily accessible and intuitive in key functionalities to users with different levels of technical knowledge. Addressing this need calls for proactive and tailored smart UI features (per user roles/types), such as notifications, alerting, or configurability, specified in detail under specific relevant Usage Requirements (UR) in the next table below.	User Interface, User Experience, System design
UN-112	The solution should be reliable and provide accurate data and performance, primarily in collection, processing and provision of pervasive/ubiquitous monitoring data and near real-time decision-supporting and proactive features (notifications, alerting), as well as in predictive analytics outputs. Complementing or overlapping multiple different sources of data, enabling cross-validation, are also beneficial for enforcing and increasing integrity.	Reliability, Performance, Sustainability
UN-113	Data security and integrity must be guaranteed. This extends not only to the common related non-functional system-level requirements (like authorization, authentication, access policies and privileges control...) having to be on industry-standard levels, but also highly domain-specific related requirements, like the secure and robust monitoring and recognition of in-situ traffic conditions by UAVs (drones), among the most comprehensive and accurate data collection and processing features as outlined already in the Project proposal, requiring highly	Security & Privacy protection

	secure cryptographically supported end-to-end message transmissions and authentication as provided by the OS-NMA protocol.	
UN-114	The costs of the service should be affordable, not requiring extra powerful computing infrastructure, nor investments on the level of value of core information systems/services used by the key existing targeted adopters (logistics and road transport stakeholders).	Performance, Sustainability

2.1.3 RDP use case requirements

The Table 2 below specifies the key functional and non-functional requirements for the envisaged SPATRA RDP pilot that addresses defined User Needs (UN), related to the satellite-based, UAV-assisted road monitoring, traffic flow, and crucial infrastructure assets availability prediction for road logistics. These requirements had been initially defined in cooperation with the stakeholder partner Nelt as the main targeted end-user (and directly and extensively available as the consortium partner on the elicitation of needs and requirements), based on their user stories, and subsequently expanded and complemented with additional ones (including also some identified needs in the table above) provided by DTS (Delta Transport Systems - www.dts.rs/home.html), an additional interested and involved international logistics, transport and distribution company, during a live definition and discussion session and follow-up on the second Stakeholder Workshop held in Belgrade, Serbia, on June 10th 2024.

Table 2 - User Requirements for RDP

Req. ID	User Requirement Name	Description	Justification and/or comment	User Need Reference
Functional				
UR-101	Ubiquitous traffic frequency monitoring	The SPATRA RDP service SHALL be able to pervasively monitor traffic conditions and frequency for congestions, resulting delays, and assets availability in the areas of interest, mainly around international border crossings, in nearest achievable to real-time temporal window.	This pervasive monitoring and data acquisition baseline functionality is crucial for the elementary service functioning, delivering the monitoring information to the end-users, and all the other dependent service features needing the data as key input.	UN-101, and indirectly most of the other identified UNs
UR-102	Combined interactive	Users SHALL interact with an intuitive geomap	Enables interaction of users with the monitoring data	UN-101,

	spatial (map) dashboard overview UI controls	with overlaid or connected relevant data presented in the same view, in intuitive tabular and diagram visualizations.	and prediction outputs in essential spatio-temporal environment and context, with intuitive data visualizations and manipulation controls.	UN-102, UN-104, UN-111
UR-103	Specifying and managing PoI and FoI	Users SHALL be able to specify, select (or deselect) specific road infrastructure features within the broad border areas of interest, for targeted monitoring. In the setup or reconfiguration for each monitored area, users can primarily confirm that preconfigured or pre-detected PoI/FoI are indeed (or are not) of their interest, as well as manually define specific additional ones (parking lots and places, road sections).	Essential PoI/FoI management functionality, and a prerequisite for targeted advanced detailed monitoring (by UAVs) of specific geographic features and points.	UN-101, UN-102, UN-111
UR-104	Provide ETA delay updates	The service SHALL provide current assessed delay in ETA at the selected border crossings or other PoI of interest, derived from as many as possible affecting diverse collected data (congestion queue length, tracked vehicle positioning, traffic flow rate...).	Provides key actionable up-to-date information for route adjustment, planning and optimization, assessed from all the usable related data detected from monitoring and relevant external datasets (accessible onsite live web cameras, weather data...).	UN-101, UN-104, UN-106, UN-111
UR-105	Ingest historical routes data from the users (their software systems)	The service SHALL support ingestion or import of historical completed route instances (with at least key positioning, timestamps,	Provides insights into ETA delay trends and variations across different routes and periods, and ground truth and reference data for comparison of delay	UN-103, UN-105, UN-106, UN-112

		and vehicle status data), to be used as baseline and ground truth data for referent routes ETA and durations.	assessments and predictions.	
UR-106	Provide ETA delay forecasts	The system SHALL be able to forecast ETA delays at selected points of interest at least 12 hours (and preferably 24 hours by default) in advance, based on collected monitoring and historical data.	Providing timely forecasting capabilities for short-term decision-making in operative route planning, adjustment and optimization.	UN-103, UN-104, UN-105, UN-108
UR-107	Forecast availability of FoI assets critical for mandatory driver breaks, like parking or rest area places	The system SHOULD be able to forecast the availability of the parking or rest area places, critical for planning mandatory driver breaks and the feasibility of complete routes, at least 12 hours (and preferably 24 hours by default) in advance, based on collected monitoring and historical data.	Providing timely forecasting capabilities for short-term and medium-term decision-making in operative route planning, adjustment and feasibility assessment.	UN-103, UN-104, UN-105, UN-108
UR-108	Forecast deviation and uncertainty levels and labelling	The system SHALL label the forecasts that deviate more than agreed acceptability levels from the post-hoc acquired actual ETA delay and availability data. The initial default levels are - within $\pm 35\%$ of the actual end-route registered time for the ETA delay, or not exceeding one calendar day	Ensures and improves the acceptable accuracy and reliability of the predictions and forecasts through continuous labelling, tracking and outliers analysis. The "tolerable" delay limits in the logistics context are more complex to determine, depend on the length of the complete route, contractual obligations towards	UN-103, UN-104, UN-105, UN-108, UN-112

		<p>- within $\pm 20\%$ of the actual observed and registered availability for the parking or rest area places.</p> <p>The labelled forecast data exceeding the defined thresholds SHOULD be easily isolated for manual and semi-automatic anomaly/outlier analysis</p>	<p>customers/clients, pre-border vs post-border delays, and other mostly human or circumstantial factors... The stated initially set threshold levels are thus to be incrementally refined, or likely even defined as configurable parameters.</p>	
UR-109	Contextualize and combine the forecasts and supporting monitoring data in presentation	<p>Users SHALL be able to view contextual information alongside the displayed forecast and monitoring data, include, at minimum, the acquisition/create timestamp, position, type and precision or resolution, and optionally extensive collected data possibly related to delays (weather, air pollution, etc.)</p>	<p>Enhances the understanding, interpretation, analysis, and improves precision and reliability of congestion trends monitoring, detection and forecasting.</p>	<p>UN-101, UN-102, UN-103, UN-104, UN-105, UN-108, UN-112</p>
UR-110	Ad-hoc and historical reports	<p>Users SHALL be provided with extensive ad-hoc and historical reporting comprising the main service outputs (ETA delays and parking availability) and joint contextual (UR-109) information, in short-term operative timeframe up to 48hours in the future, as well as in long timeline with all the past data.</p> <p>Supported interaction with the reports will comprise at least showing/hiding, sorting, filtering, and</p>	<p>Enables exploration, checks and verifications within the complete historical data for long-term trend analysis and planning while also supporting short-term insights and decision-making.</p>	<p>UN-106, UN-107, UN-111, UN-112</p>

		grouping or aggregation per selected applicable data or time columns (like per PoI border crossings, or sorting per calculated ETA delay explicitly given as needed examples by the users), and selection for export/download.		
UR-111	Export/download report data	Users SHALL be able to download the generated report data in tabular or graph form. The download of data in common data formats SHALL be supported.	Enhances interoperability by allowing seamless integration with other tools, and provides users with flexibility in custom analysis of data, facilitating collaboration and decision-making processes. The formats should include delimited text, JSON, xls/xlsx, PDF, and PNG.	UN-106, UN-107, UN-111, UN-112
UR-112	Enable input of future known high likelihoods of congestions and delays, and use the inputs for alerting, and for validation and improvement of predictions	Users SHOULD be able to enter (and subsequently edit, amend or delete) in the system periods or patterns of high likelihood of congestions and delays at specific points or areas known in advance (customs shift change periods, procedure updates or introductions). Input or interactive marking in the calendar or timeline SHOULD also support the entry of recurring periodic anticipated delays.	Input of known highly likely (practically labelled) future upcoming congestion events should, beside the direct use for later alerting/notifications, serve for checking, validation and improvement of predictions, as well as for deeper understanding of trends and causes of congestions.	UN-103, UN-104, UN-110, UN-111, UN-112
UR-113	Notifications/ Alerting	Users SHALL be able to subscribe to alerts/notifications on detected or highly likely	A key feature for enhancing proactive and preventive decision making and efficiency. Users can	UN-104, UN-111

		<p>congestions, delays, or unavailability of parking places in selected areas of interest.</p> <p>Notification/Alerts SHOULD also be sent via mail or direct text message (additionally to being displayed in the service UI directly).</p>	<p>take necessary actions promptly upon notification.</p>	
UR-114	<p>On-demand most accurate (drone-based) real-time congestion and parking availability detection</p>	<p>The service SHALL provide the possibility of a not necessarily pervasive but more accurate and reliable direct in-situ detection (or verification) of assets and features of interest than achievable by the combined EO and supporting techniques enabling pervasive monitoring (as expressed in UN-101, UN-102 and UR-102 above). This on-demand direct detection can conveniently be performed by secure and robust observing UAVs stationed/docked in border areas, and engaged to flight when needed, controlled and managed by the RDS service.</p>	<p>The drone-assessed road monitoring is one of the 3 key applied innovations of the SPATRA RDS solution, along with monitoring and detection using satellite/EO data, and prediction and inferencing based on historical time-series data.</p>	<p>UN-101, UN-102, UN-103, UN-111, UN-112, UN-113</p>
UR-115	<p>Extensive domain logic configurability</p>	<p>The system SHOULD support comprehensive user-configurability of most of the key driving parameters of RDP-specific domain logic supporting the main required functionalities stated in the previous</p>	<p>Very important for the usability, user-friendliness, scalability and adaptability, and overall integration and exploitation potential of the solution.</p>	<p>UN-108, UN-110, UN-111</p>

		requirements above - namely the configurability (and extensibility where applicable) of the domain codebooks (FoI, PoI and monitored asset types, units etc.), prediction, forecasting and assessment parameters (timeframes, precision or uncertainty levels, etc.), notification and alerting settings (timeframes and ranges, frequency, communication channels etc.), reporting preferences, and others specified by the end users.		
Non-functional				
UR-116	Infrastructural configurability	The system SHOULD support configurability and seamless additions/extensions of its key infrastructural assets (data sources, metadata records, codebooks and classifiers, integrated or connected hardware/IoT devices, etc.)	A feature of crucial importance for scalability, extensibility, adaptability, and overall sustainability and ease of maintenance of the system in exploitation.	UN-108, UN-111, UN-112
UR-117	Authentication/ Authorization	Users SHALL log in securely using their credentials following industry standards.	Ensures that only authorized users can access sensitive data, maintaining data security, integrity and access control by utilizing industry standards such as OAuth 2.0, UMA, or RFC 7519 JWT.	UN-112, UN-113
UR-118	Data Integrity	The system SHALL ensure the integrity of all data stored, processed, and transmitted within the	Data integrity is paramount as safety decisions and operational actions are	UN-113

		system. This includes detailed operations and transactions auditing, and measures to prevent unauthorized access, modification, or deletion of data.	based on the accuracy and reliability of the data.	
UR-119	Performance and scalability	The system SHALL be able to seamlessly scale with supplied additional resources in response to the user demands and loads.	Ensures that the system remains responsive and performant, regardless of variations in user demand and handled data and requests load.	UN-106, UN-107, UN-111, UN-112, UN-114
UR-120	System integration and interoperability	The system SHOULD be able to integrate as much as possible with the existing related and relevant core ICT infrastructure (tools, system...) on the end-user side.	Enhances usability, efficiency, user-friendliness, learning speed, and overall exploitation potential of the SPATRA services and tools by leveraging existing used and well-understood systems.	UN-111, UN-114
UR-121	Documentation	Users SHOULD get a well-explained documentation of its interfaces and data products, algorithms and processing steps and the usage. Customer helpdesk support during working hours MAY also be desirable.	Aids users in understanding and utilizing the system effectively.	UN-111, UN-114

2.2 Railway monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings pilot use case (RWP)

2.2.1 RWP use case description

The escalating severity and occurrence of extreme weather events, driven by climate change, pose significant risks to the reliability of rail services. Such conditions can lead to the deformation of rail tracks and even cause train derailments. High temperatures, in particular, can cause rails to expand, warp, and potentially fracture, a phenomenon known as "rail buckling" as shown in Figure 2. For instance, Network Rail's tracks are designed to endure a "stress-free" temperature of 27 °C, reflecting the average summer rail temperature in the UK. While sections of the track resting on concrete sleepers that meet Network Rail's standards can resist elevated rail temperatures, there are segments that are not equipped to handle such intense heat and are therefore susceptible to buckling. The UK's railway network spans approximately 32,187 km, with a significant portion directly exposed to sunlight. Network Rail, the entity responsible for managing Britain's railway infrastructure, has observed that tracks under direct sunlight can reach temperatures up to 20 °C higher than the surrounding air. As temperatures soar, the steel rails absorb heat and expand, leading to rail deflection and eventually buckling. These distorted tracks require immediate repair to restore train services, resulting in operational disruptions. Additionally, overhead power lines are prone to expansion and sagging in extreme heat, heightening the risk of being pulled down by passing trains. In UK alone, in the last 20 years there were 11 derailments connected to rail buckling. Although the "stress-free" temperature is higher in Southern Europe, the magnitude of this issue is even more pronounced in regions known for its exceptionally high temperatures like Andalusia, Castilla-La Mancha, Alentejo, Sicily and Sardinia. Historical data indicates a rising trend in track buckling incidents correlating with rising average temperatures and more frequent heatwaves.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. a) Lateral buckling of the track due to high temperatures, Slovenia³. (b) Typical example of track buckle, UK⁴.

³ Palin, E.J.; Stipanovic Oslakovic, I.; Gavin, K.; Quinn, A. Implications of climate change for railway infrastructure. *Wiley Interdiscip.Rev. Clim. Chang.* 2021, 12, e728.

⁴ Johnson, T. Network Rail announces six design winners of remote track buckle detection contest, www.newcivilengineer.com, accessed on

Without planning, the measures to prevent track buckling (such as reducing the train speed or watering the tracks) might disrupt the train-operating schedule and create blockages or traffic jams. For instance, on the UK's hottest July day ever, there were 12,800 delay minutes from heat and another 23,700 min from unexpected train-speed limits. If the rail temperature and the rail buckling risk in an area can be forecasted in advance, rail management can set the speed limit of the train, change the gaps between trains, or cool the rail by suitable methods like water spraying, which can improve train punctuality and track safety. Using satellite data could enable services for finding the railway areas that are most affected by severe impacts from weather events. Combining space-based rail temperature prediction with decision-making model for rail buckling risk can enable service for effective management.

The problem SPATRA aims to address is how to make rail transport more efficient by better predicting where rail tracks can overheat and avoiding unnecessary slow train orders. This is a big issue for Serbia and the West Balkan region, where summers are very hot and rail tracks often get damaged or deformed by heat. Maintenance costs go up and safety risks increase. Also, most of the rail tracks in Serbia and nearby countries have wooden sleepers which due to lower rigidity can't handle high temperatures and may cause rail buckling. For example, in one week in 2017 when the air temperature was around 40°C, there were 31 rail track deformations in Serbia because the rail tracks got as hot as 60°C⁵. Development and validation of SPATRA RWP is fully supported by Serbian Railway Infrastructure, who has been involved in the project from its onset. The following User Needs and Requirements were defined in cooperation with Serbian Railway Infrastructure.

2.2.2 RWP user needs and challenges

Table 3 below lists the user needs identified after the evaluation of the outcomes of the user stories collected through different contact channels: online interviews, questionnaires and the Workshop. The main consulted stakeholder and end-user was Serbian Railway Infrastructure, who is fully supporting all SPATRA project activities as the main Advisory Board member. Besides Serbian Railway Infrastructure, different stakeholders were consulted, such as Transport Community⁶, an international organisation in the field of mobility and transport who is working on integrating Western Balkans' transport markets into the EU. Table below represents a list of consolidated user needs.

Table 3 - User needs description for RWP

ID	User Need Description	UN category
UN-201	A method for prediction of the rail track temperature (RTT) at a large scale (for the whole network) that will provide better accuracy for the local track sections temperature measuring is needed.	Data Analysis - Rail Temperature Prediction

⁵ <https://www.blic.rs/vesti/drustvo/zeleznica-srbije-velike-vrucine-krive-koloseke-i-prave-probleme-u-naponu/hedr3v7>

⁶ <https://www.transport-community.org/>

UN-202	The risk of buckling needs to be assessed and predicted.	Data Analysis - Buckling Risk Assessment
UN-203	Temperature trends should be analysed.	Data Analysis
UN-204	The service shall be customisable in regard to locations and time intervals for which temperature need to be provided and scale accordingly.	Scalability
UN-205	A high spatial resolution of 500m per pixel or finer is needed to model temperature variations along the railway network with sufficient accuracy. Additionally, comprehensive observation of the entire network is imperative for effective modelling.	Data Constraints
UN-206	Multiple/hourly temperature data points should be provided.	Data Constraints
UN-207	A rail temperature forecast of up to 24 hours is needed.	Data Constraints
UN-208	The temperature prediction deviation from the actual temperature should not exceed 5°C.	Data Constraints
UN-209	Critical Rail Temperatures (CRT) should be calculated based on track curvature and track parameters.	Data Analysis - Buckling Risk Assessment
UN-210	Parts of rail track where RTT is larger than CRT should be highlighted.	User Interface
UN-211	Rail lateral deformation should be predicted based on RTT and track parameters.	Data Analysis - Buckling Risk Assessment
UN-212	Access to raw data (e.g. temperature data) should be provided.	Data Access
UN-213	The temperature measurement service should be able to be integrated into or compatible with the existing system.	System Integration
UN-214	The service needs to be user-friendly and easily accessible to users with different levels of technical knowledge.	User Interface

UN-215	The solution should be reliable and provide accurate data and performance.	Reliability, Performance
UN-216	Data security and integrity must be guaranteed.	Data Security/Integrity
UN-217	The costs of the service must be affordable.	Data Constraints

2.2.3 RWP use case requirements

The Table 4 outlines a set of functional (UFR) and nonfunctional (UNFR) requirements for the envisaged SPATRA RWP service that address defined User Needs (UN), related to the Satellite-based monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings use case. These requirements were defined in cooperation with the end-user, Serbian Railway Infrastructure, based on their user story collected during the end-user consultations in beginning months of the project.

Table 4 - User Requirements for SPATRA RWP service

Req. ID	User Requirement Name	Description	Justification and/or comment	User Need Ref.
Functional				
UR-201	Interactive map	Users SHALL interact with an intuitive railway map.	Provides users with an intuitive and visual means of selecting rail track segments and assessing temperature conditions in context of their geographic locations.	UN-214
UR-202	Register rail track segments	Users SHALL be able to register, browse, select, edit, and delete rail track segments and timeframes effectively creating rail track buckling risk (RTBR) tasks for collecting RTBR data from the past, present and future.	Allows users to manage rail track segments and timeframes for RTBR monitoring, especially segments which are prone to temperature related	UN-201, UN-202, UN-204, UN-205, UN-206, UN-207.

			issues such as buckling.	UN-209, UN-211
UR-203	Integrate user data	<p>Users SHALL be able to integrate their data into the system, including, at minimum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Track properties: integrate user specific track specification for RTBR task. - Visual support: overlay user data onto the base map for visual reference and analysis. - RTBR task registration support: register pre-defined rail track segments and RTBR tasks provided by the user. - RTBR/RTT time series generation support: include geolocations and datetimes of critical points to generate time series data. 	Promotes efficiency and scalability by providing users with the ability to integrate their data in bulk.	UN-204, UN-209, UN-211
UR-204	Define thresholds	Users SHALL be able to define, edit and delete CRT thresholds for all locations on the selected RTBR task.	Provides a mechanism for setting the CRT for different locations along the rail track. This feature allows users to monitor temperature levels effectively and take preventive actions when thresholds are exceeded.	UN-209, UN-214
UR-205	Display RTBR and RTT data	Users SHALL be able to select and view the processed RTBR and RTT data from the RTBR task as an image or a video overlaid onto the	Enables quick access to real-time updates, which is crucial for addressing heat-	UN-201, UN-202, UN-206,

		<p>base map as soon as it is processed. Parts of the rail track where RTT is larger than CRT SHALL be highlighted.</p> <p>The data SHALL be displayed either in raw or aggregated form.</p> <p>Users SHALL be able to select and view intermediate results, including raw and downscaled LST data.</p>	<p>related issues such as buckling.</p>	<p>UN-207, UN-210, UN-214</p>
UR-206	Display RTBR and RTT time series	<p>Users SHALL be able to select, edit and delete locations on the displayed RTBR and RTT data and view the time series specified by the selected RTBR task.</p> <p>The time series MAY be displayed as a line graph.</p> <p>Users SHALL be able to select several locations at the same time and view the visibly assignable time series graphs in one figure.</p> <p>Additionally, users SHALL be able to aggregate the time series data for any selected location and RTBR task.</p>	<p>Provides insights into temperature trends and variations along different sections of the track. This feature empowers users to identify RTBR/RTT patterns, anomalies, and potential areas of concern, facilitating proactive maintenance and operational decision-making.</p>	<p>UN-203, UN-206, UN-207, UN-210, UN-214</p>
UR-207	Contextualize data	<p>Users SHALL be able to view contextual information alongside the displayed RTBR and RTT data. This information SHALL include, at minimum, the datetime and weather conditions such as air temperature, precipitation, and cloud coverage.</p>	<p>Enhances the understanding and interpretation of temperature and buckling trends.</p>	<p>UN-214</p>

UR-208	Temporal constraints on derived RTBR and RTT data	The system SHALL be able to derive/forecast hourly RTBR and RTT data with associated uncertainties for up to 5 years into the past and 24 hours into the future.	Allows to access historical RTBR and RTT data for long-term trend analysis and planning while also providing near-real-time forecasting capabilities for short-term decision-making.	UN-201, UN-202, UN-206, UN-207
UR-209	Spatial constraints on derived RTBR and RTT data	The system SHALL be able to derive/forecast RTBR and RTT data with a high spatial resolution of 500m per pixel or finer.	Improves granularity. Finer resolutions enable more precise monitoring and analysis of temperature variations, contributing to better-informed decision-making for rail track maintenance and operations.	UN-201, UN-202, UN-205
UR-210	Uncertainty constraints on derived RTT data	The system SHALL ensure that the uncertainties of the derived/forecasted RTT data does not exceed 5°C. Moreover, it SHOULD be able to identify anomalies in the data.	Ensures the accuracy and reliability of RTT and RTBR predictions.	UN-201, UN-208, UN-215
UR-211	Timeliness constraints on derived RTBR/RTT data	The system SHALL ensure that critical input data, such as LST and weather condition data, used in the processing steps for deriving RTT and RTBR data are the most recent available data and not older than 4 hours.	Minimize the need for forecasting based on outdated data. This constraint enhances the accuracy and reliability of derived temperature data by ensuring that it reflects current	UN-215

			<p>conditions as closely as possible.</p> <p>Moreover, timely delivery of derived and forecasted RTT and RTBR data, allows users to make informed decisions in a timely manner.</p>	
UR-212	Update forecasted data	The system SHALL update the forecasted RTT and RTBR data and the associated uncertainties on an hourly basis.	Reduces uncertainties.	UN-206, UN-215
UR-213	Use open institutional input data	The system SHALL use open institutional data to ensure data integrity and affordability.	Copernicus data sources such as CDSE and CMLS satisfy this requirement.	UN-217
UR-214	Download RTBR and RTT data	Users SHALL be able to download the displayed RTBR and RTT data into common data formats.	Enhances interoperability and facilitates further analysis or integration with other tools. The Formats should include cloud-optimized GEOTIFF, ZARR, NETCDF, PNG and MP4.	UN-209, UN-213
UR-215	Download time series	Users SHALL be able to download the displayed time series data and their corresponding graphs. The downloaded data SHALL be available in common data formats.	Enhances interoperability by allowing seamless integration with other tools. This feature provides users with flexibility in analysing and sharing data, facilitating collaboration and decision-making	UN-209, UN-213

			processes. The formats should include CSV, JSON, Excel, PDF and PNG.	
UR-216	Analyse RTBR and RTT data and time series	Users SHALL be able to view and download a table containing RTBR and RTT values, their differences with the predefined thresholds, datetime and locations of all threshold-exceeding data points in the displayed RTBR and RTT data or time series. The downloaded table SHALL be available in common data formats.	Facilitates user assessment of the displayed data through targeted filtering and focus on only the critical data points. The formats should include CSV, JSON, Excel, PDF, and PNG.	UN-203, UN-212, UN-213
UR-217	Analyse trends	Users SHALL be able to view the RTBR and RTT trend for any selected location within the chosen RTBR task.	Empowers users to evaluate future risk levels of specific locations, aiding in proactive planning and decision-making processes.	UN-203, UN-214
UR-218	Notifications/ Alerts	Users SHALL be able to subscribe to alerts/notifications about completion of RTBR tasks, RTBR/RTT data points passing thresholds and spotted anomalies. Notification/ Alerts SHOULD be sent via mail and displayed in the service directly.	Enhances efficiency. Users can take necessary actions promptly upon notification. This includes RTBR/RTT data points that exceed thresholds, as well as those that fall below them due to updated forecast RTBR/RTT data.	UN-214
Nonfunctional				

UR-219	Authentication/ Authorization	Users SHALL log in securely using their credentials following industry standards.	Ensures that only authorized users can access sensitive data, maintaining data integrity and confidentiality by utilizing industry standards such as OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect.	UN-216
UR-220	Data Integrity	The system SHALL ensure the integrity of all data stored, processed, and transmitted within the system. This includes measures to prevent unauthorized access, modification, or deletion of data.	Data integrity is paramount as safety decisions and operational actions are based on the accuracy and reliability of the data.	UN-216
UR-221	Scalability	The system SHALL be able to scale in response to the user demands.	Ensures that the system remains responsive and performant, regardless of variations in user demand.	UN-204
UR-222	System Integration	The system SHOULD be able to integrate with the existing user system.	Enhances learning speed by leveraging existing and well-understood systems.	UN-213
UR-223	Documentation	Users SHOULD get a well-explained documentation of its interfaces and data products, algorithms and processing steps and the usage. Customer helpdesk support during working hours MAY also be desirable.	Aids users in understanding and utilizing the system effectively.	UN-214

2.3 SPATRA system requirements

In this section, a set of system requirements is defined to describe the considered SPATRA RDP and RWP services and how these shall fulfil the defined User Requirements for both service pilots as listed in Table 2 and Table 4. The indicative priority of the requirements in sense what should be developed first and what later is denoted with H – high, M -medium and L – low.

Table 5 below describes the preliminary System Requirements (SR) defined to fulfil the User Requirements (UR).

Table 5 – SPATRA system requirements

ID	System Requirement	Priority	Description	User Req.	Use case (UC)
SR-001	API Gateway	H	The system SHALL manage the external API request in a centralized manner. This includes authentication, authorization, routing, load balancing, service discovery, caching, user input validation and transformation, API versioning.	UR-115 UR-116 UR-119 UR-120 UR-219 UR-220 UR-221 UR-222	RDP RWP
SR-002	Web-Based Interface and Responsive Design	H	The system SHALL offer a web-based graphical interface (WebGUI) accessible via standard web browsers and SHOULD provide a responsive design that adapts to various screen sizes and devices.	UR-101 UR-201	RDP RWP
SR-003	Interactive Maps and Layer Management	M	The system SHALL centre around interactive maps and provide multiple switchable layers, including Open Street Map, Open Railway Map, and satellite imagery.	UR-101 UR-115 UR-201	RDP RWP
SR-004	User Authentication and Login	H	The WebGUI SHALL provide a login button that redirects users to the Identity Provider's login page. Upon successful login, users SHALL be redirected back to the WebGUI with the login	UR-113 UR-118 UR-219	RDP RWP

			button replaced by a user account information/logout button.		
SR-005	User Data Management and Overlay	M	The WebGUI SHALL allow users to upload, browse, select, download, delete and overlay their own vector and alphanumeric data within the WebGUI. At a minimum, the WebGUI SHALL support the GEOJSON format for vector data.	UR-105 UR-201 UR-203	RDP RWP
SR-006	RTBR Task and Subtask Management	H	The WebGUI SHALL provide a graphical interface for RTBR task CRUD operations and enable users to browse, select, edit, and delete RTBR tasks and subtasks. It SHALL display metadata and allow for the download of metadata.	UR-202	RWP
SR-007	Data Visualization, Interaction and Contextualization	M	The Web GUI SHALL visualize the footprint and data of selected RTBR subtask assets and RDP monitored assets, including adding a colour bar with configurable colour map and value range/scale. It MAY provide a slider interface for visualizing RTT and RTBR data together. Moreover, contextual information SHALL be displayed and include, at minimum, the datetime and weather conditions such as air temperature, precipitation, and cloud coverage.	UR-109 UR-110 UR-205 UR-207	RDP RWP
SR-008	Aggregated Time Series Visualization and Download	H	Users SHALL be able to select multiple POIs and AOIs on the map for a selected RTBR subtask or RDP monitored asset, choose an aggregation method and target granularity, and visualize the aggregated POI and AOI time series. The system SHALL enable the download of the displayed time series in common data formats such as CSV, JSON, PDF, and PNG.	UR-103 UR-110 UR-111 UR-115 UR-216	RDP RWP
SR-009	Notifications & alerting Management	H	The Web GUI SHALL provide features for viewing, filtering, and managing notifications. It SHALL display pop-up notifications for new alerts and show a count of unread notifications. Users SHALL be able to configure their notification preferences, including additional channels such as RSS and email.	UR-112 UR-113 UR-115 UR-218	RDP RWP

SR-010	Data Catalog API	H	The system SHALL implement a Data Catalog API responsible for providing STAC API endpoints, supporting CRUD operations for RTBR tasks and user vector data, and querying metadata of finished RTBR subtasks and their tasks.	UR-202 UR-205 UR-214 UR-215 UR-216 UR-217	RWP
SR-011	Job Management	M	The system SHALL implement a Job Manager responsible for distributing jobs to the responsible components, scaling components based on job resource consumption, supporting job parameter modification, prioritizing jobs, monitoring and reporting job status, resuming interrupted jobs.	UR-211 UR-221	RWP
SR-012	Data Discovery	H	The system SHALL implement a Data Discovery component responsible for monitoring all data sources for newly published data.	UR-211 UR-212 UR-213	RWP
SR-013	Processor Job Generation	H	The system SHALL implement a Processor Job Generation component responsible for generating RTBR subtasks and RTBR tile-subtasks from the RTBR tasks and creating STAC collections and item templates for the RTBR tile-subtasks.	UR-202 UR-213	RWP
SR-014	Data Collection, Access, Harmonization and Contextualization	H	The system SHALL be able to collect, access, download and harmonize all data products listed in the sections 3.1.2.1 (for the RWP UC) and 3.2.4 (for the RWP UC) from specified Data Sources. Where possible, the system SHOULD only download the data sections that intersect the AOI. Also it SHALL add contextual information to the data. This information SHALL include, at minimum, the datetime and weather conditions such as air temperature, precipitation, and cloud coverage.	UR-109 UR-114 UR-213	RDP RWP
SR-015	Data Processing	H	The system SHALL clip, reproject, and mosaic the source data product tiles according to the target AOI, Coordinate Reference System	UR-202	RWP

	and Masking		(CRS), and grid. Additionally, the system SHALL be able to mask data if required, with cloud, land cover, and quality flag masking implemented at minimum. Moreover, the system SHALL be able to apply formulas for indices such as NDVI and NDBI.		
SR-016	Thermal Data Downscaling Methods	H	The system SHALL implement LST downscaling approaches suitable for near-real time applications, including at minimum a kernel-based algorithm. Additionally, it MAY implement a spatio-temporal downscaling algorithm for historical time series data to improve performance.	UR-205	RWP
SR-017	Rail Track Temperature Prediction	H	The system SHALL implement a rail track temperature prediction model suitable for near-real time rail track temperature prediction.	UR-205	RWP
SR-018	Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment	H	The system SHALL implement a rail track buckling risk assessment model. The risk of buckling SHALL be assessed and categorized into three levels: no risk, low risk, and high risk, based on the comparison between the predicted rail track temperature and CRT.	UR-205	RWP
SR-019	User Data for Buckling Risk Assessment	L	The rail track buckling risk assessment model MAY include the user vector data as additional input data for the risk assessment. Especially, if it contains information on the rail track materials and state.	UR-203	RWP
SR-020	RTT/RTBR Prediction - Temporal Resolution	H	The system SHALL provide hourly RTT and RTBR predictions for a 24-hour forecast window and for up to 5 years into the past.	UR-205 UR-208	RWP
SR-021	RTT/RTBR Prediction - Update	M	The system SHALL update the forecasted RTT and RTBR data with the associated uncertainties on an hourly basis.	UR-205 UR-212	RWP

	forecasted data				
SR-022	Data Quality Assessment	L	The system SHALL assess the quality of incoming data based on predefined quality metrics.	UR-210	RWP
SR-023	Threshold Monitoring	H	The system SHALL continuously compare the predicted RTT values against predefined thresholds.	UR-204 UR-210	RWP
SR-024	Anomaly Detection	M	The system SHALL implement anomaly detection algorithms to identify unusual patterns or outliers in the data.	UR-210	RWP
SR-025	Notifications via RSS feed and e-mail	L	The system SHOULD send notifications via RSS feed and e-mail if requested by the user.	UR-113 UR-115 UR-218 UR-220	RDP RWP
SR-026	Metadata evaluation for needed notifications	L	The Notification and Alerts component SHALL be able evaluate the metadata of the finished RTBR subtask and create notification messages for the user if needed.	UR-218	RWP
SR-027	XYZ Tiles Service with configurable colormaps	H	The system provides an XYZ tiles service for delivering images of raster data assets from the STAC catalogue. Additionally, it SHOULD offer capabilities to configure colormaps and their value range and scale.	UR-205	RWP
SR-028	POI Data Values and Aggregate Time Series	H	The system SHALL provide Time Series Analytics API as a RESTful API. This API SHALL supply POI data values and aggregate time series data from the data catalogue for specified AOIs and POIs. It SHALL support aggregation with a granularity of up to hourly intervals and include statistical operations such as maximum, minimum, mean, median, and count. The API SHALL also allow applying conditions such as threshold exceedance.	UR-105 UR-110 UR-206 UR-215 UR-216 UR-217	RDP RWP

SR-029	Trend Analysis	M	The Time Series Analytics API SHALL provide trend analysis of the aggregated time series data for specified AOIs. It SHALL compute and return a single numerical value representing the overall trend.	UR-215 UR-217	RWP
SR-030	Single access point to object storage	M	The system SHOULD implement a Data Gateway as a single access point to the object storage for all CRUD operations.	UR-221	RWP
SR-031	Identity and Access Management	M	The system SHALL implement a comprehensive Identity and Access Management solution that includes a robust Identity Provider component. This component SHALL support user authentication, account management and authorization, in particular to enable role-based access control to provide granular access control to resources.	UR-113 UR-118 UR-219 UR-220 UR-221 UR-223	RDP RWP
SR-032	Cache	L	The system SHALL implement caching. It SHALL store frequently accessed data to reduce access times and load on the primary data source. It SHALL provide mechanisms for quick and efficient data retrieval, support cache invalidation to prevent serving stale data, and include configurable expiration policies (TTL and TTI). It SHALL ensure data consistency with the primary data source using strategies like write-through or write-back caching, support data eviction policies (LRU, LFU, FIFO), and provide statistics and metrics on cache usage, hit/miss rates, and performance.	UR-221	RWP
SR-033	Comprehensive Logging and Metrics Monitoring System	H	The system SHALL implement a robust and scalable logging and metrics monitoring solution that collects, processes, analyzes, and visualizes data from all system components. This solution SHALL support real-time monitoring, historical analysis, alerting, and reporting capabilities to ensure system health, performance, and security.	UR-108 UR-109 UR-110 UR-111 UR-205 UR-210	RDP RWP

				UR-211 UR-223	
SR-034	Time Behavior - WebGUI	M	The WebGUI SHALL load within 2 seconds for users under normal circumstances.	UR-106 UR-107 UR-111 UR-221	RDP RWP
SR-035	Time Behavior - Data Catalog API	M	The Data Catalog API SHALL ensure a response time of less than 300 milliseconds for typical queries and CRUD operations.	UR-211	RWP
SR-036	Time Behavior - Timeliness of Data Discovery	H	New data SHALL be discovered no later than 5 minutes after publication.	UR-211	RWP
SR-037	Functional Accuracy/Time Behavior - RTBR tile-subtask tiling size	H	The tiling size of the RTBR tile-subtasks SHALL depend on the spatial and temporal resolutions of the data products. The sizes need to be chosen such that all timeliness requirements can be met.	UR-211 UR-221	RWP
SR-038	Analysability - Comprehensive item templates	M	The item templates SHALL include fields for verbose information about data sources, used data product instances, versions of processors to be used, intermediate results at least in vrt format, previews, item summaries as plots, statistics, verification and validation results.	UR-213 UR-220	RWP
SR-039	Analysability - Comprehensive processor metadata and previews	L	The Processors SHOULD include their version information in the metadata of the data they process, provide previews of the processed image data assets. Moreover they MAY include intermediate images in VRT format.	n.a.	RWP

SR-040	Resource Utilization and Time Behavior Optimization - Window Operations	H	The processor components that work with raster data SHALL use a moving window approach for image processing wherever applicable to decrease the maximal memory consumption. Additionally, the system SHOULD parallelize window operations for the same image wherever applicable.	n.a.	RDP RWP
SR-041	Modifiability - Quick integration of new data sources	M	The system SHALL be implemented such that new data sources and products can be integrated quickly.	UR-213	RWP
SR-042	Fault Tolerance - Retry at data unavailability	L	The system SHOULD incorporate retry policies for downloading the data from the Data Sources.	n.a.	RWP
SR-043	Functional Appropriateness - High spatial resolution	H	The Thermal Downscaling SHALL improve the spatial resolution of coarse resolution LST data to a high resolution of 500m or finer. This SHALL be done at minimum for Sentinel-3 (1km), Aqua/Terra MODIS (1km) and CLMS (5km).	UR-209	RWP
SR-044	Time Behavior - Thermal Downscaling	M	The Thermal Downscaling SHALL be completed in less than 30 minutes.	n.a.	RWP
SR-045	Functional Correctness - Thermal Downscaling Accuracy	M	The downscaled temperatures SHALL be within 3 °C of the actual temperature.	n.a.	RWP

SR-046	Time Behavior - RTT Prediction	M	The Rail Track Temperature Prediction SHALL be completed in less than 10 minutes.	UR-205 UR-208	RWP
SR-047	Functional Correctness - RTT Prediction Accuracy	M	The predicted RTT SHALL not deviate from the actual temperature by more than 5°C.	UR-210	RWP
SR-048	Time Behavior - Buckling Risk Assessment	M	The Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment component SHALL perform risk assessments for all monitored track segments within 1 minute of receiving new rail temperature data.	n.a.	RWP
SR-049	Time Behavior - Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring	M	The Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring component SHALL process and analyze data in near real-time, with a maximum delay of 1 minute from data receipt to analysis completion.	n.a.	RWP
SR-050	Time Behavior - Timeliness of notifications	L	The Notification and Alerts component SHALL send notifications over all channels within 10 seconds from ingestion of the metadata of the finished RTBR subtask.	UR-218	RWP
SR-051	Time Behavior - Map Tiles	L	The XYZ service SHALL deliver image tiles within 2 seconds to ensure a responsive and smooth user experience.	UR-205	RWP
SR-052	Time Behavior – Time Series Analytics	L	The Time Series Analytics API SHALL provide POI data values time series within 100 milliseconds and deliver time series and trend analysis data within 5 minutes per year.	UR-105 UR-110 UR-206 UR-217	RDP RWP

SR-053	Modifiability – Data Gateway	L	The Data Gateway SHALL be implemented to enable quick switching of the object storage provider.	UR-221	RWP
SR-054	Time Behavior - Timely Data Processing	M	The system SHALL complete the processing steps for a RTBR tile-subtask within 1 hour.	UR-211 UR-212	RWP
SR-055	Time Behavior - Timeliness Constraints	M	The system SHALL ensure that critical input data, such as LST and weather condition data, used in the processing steps for deriving RTT and RTBR data are the most recent available data and not older than 4 hours.	UR-211	RWP
SR-056	Time Behavior - Historical Data Retrieval	L	The system SHALL make historical RTBR/RTT data for rail track segments of 100km length for an one year interval, going back up to 5 years, available within 1 day of user request.	UR-208	RWP
SR-057	Scalability	L	The system SHALL be able to scale up to handle an increase in data volume due to the addition of rail track segments up to 1000km.	UR-221	RWP
SR-058	Recoverability	L	The system SHALL make backups of all relevant data. Moreover, it SHALL gracefully handle and recover from unexpected errors or crashes without data loss.	UR-118 UR-119	RDP RWP
SR-059	Faultlessness	L	The system SHALL maintain alternative data sources for all critical data inputs if applicable. If no alternative data source is available, the system SHALL promptly communicate the unavailability to the user through the WebGUI.	UR-115 UR-118 UR-213	RDP RWP
SR-060	Interoperability - Data Formats	H	The system SHALL support the following data format requirements: - Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG): The system SHALL provide raster data in the COG format.	UR-214	RWP

			<p>- ZARR: Optionally, the system MAY provide raster data in the ZARR format to enhance the performance of time series analysis.</p> <p>- STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog): The system SHALL encode RTBR tasks, RTBR subtasks, and metadata of the raster data as STAC objects.</p>		
SR-061	Modifiability - Versioning	M	All components and interfaces SHALL implement versioning. The available versions SHALL be documented clearly at a central location.	UR-118	RDP RWP
SR-062	Usability	M	The system SHALL provide an intuitive user interface that allows new users to complete the rail track segment registration process within 5 minutes without assistance.	UR-223	RWP
SR-063	Documentation	M	The system SHALL provide comprehensive documentation of its interfaces, data products, algorithms, and processing steps to aid user understanding and system utilization.	UR-121 UR-223	RDP RWP
SR-064	Interoperability - Data Formats	M	<p>The system SHALL support the following common standard data/file formats in conversion and export features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - plain text (.txt, .csv), and JSON or XML for alphanumeric data - Microsoft Excel formats (.xls, .xlsx) for tabular data - .png or .pdf for image data (export/output only) - GeoJSON or COG for spatial data 	UR-111	RDP
SR-065	Time Behavior - ETA Delay Assessment /Prediction	H	The ETA delay assessment/prediction SHALL be completed in less than 2 minutes.	UR-104 UR-106 UR-108 UR-113	RDP

SR-066	System – architecture scalability	M	The different backend services SHALL be designed in a modular and stateless fashion such that they can run separately and independently.	UR-101 UR-102 UR-201 UR-204	RDP RWP
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3 USE CASE TECHNICAL DEVELOPMENT SPECIFICATION

3.1 SPATRA road infrastructure monitoring pilot system definition and operational context

3.1.1 RDP high-level service system architecture

The overall RDP-supporting broad system organization and modular 4-tiered service architecture concept is presented on the diagram below, along with the main external input sources and the stakeholders it serves or interacts with:

Figure 3. High-level RDP-supporting system architecture and organization

The **SPATRA RDP Core** in the centre of the diagram in Figure 3 represents the principally envisioned minimum viable product (MVP) - the standalone RDP-supporting system with:

- Core essential data collection, management and provision, and integration functionalities handled by the **Service Middleware**. The specific back-end service packages and module groups on this layer are divided into two main types per functional specificity and addressed requirement types:
 - **Domain-specific** encompass the logic supporting the specific RDP use case processes in the road freight transport and logistics, and applicable related domains, and mainly

the Functional user requirements and needs specified in the relevant sections 2.1.1, 2.1.2, 2.1.3 and 2.2.3 above – ETA delay computation, route optimisation, acquired data validations and consistency maintenance, etc.

- **Orthogonal** cover more generic systemic infrastructure functionalities transversal across the other tiers, like security, general data persistence and retrieval, interoperability, performance, and related catering mostly to the specified *Non-functional* user requirements and needs stated in the relevant sections above, modular but mostly tightly coupled with the domain-specific service packages, like, for example, the Notifications/alerting & Scheduling module, being fed by the *Applicative data provision services* with the logistics-specific content to be propagated to the end users.
- The **Analytics** tier is planned modular and separated from the Service Middleware, as it will mostly cover clearly encapsulated analytic and ML functionalities directly corresponding to the requirements SR-034 and SR-065 (and SR-066 in general) from 2.3 above - trucks, assets and FoI detection, image enhancement and recognition, and predictive models training and refining - as well as for easier portability and support for additional and different programming language(s) in the implementation.
- The cloud **Data Repository** foundation tier is to store all relevant data acquired or generated by the system, known at this stage to be including a heterogeneous range - from unstructured data such as raster images, to highly structured relational domain-specific data and metadata, and time-series data in variable temporal resolutions, from raw IoT/sensory streams to notification/alerting messages.
- The interactive application for road traffic flow monitoring and predicting is intended to be the main UI tool for the end users on the **Front-end** tier, possibly integrated with the existing external monitoring or logistics management software tools of key targeted end-users such as Nelt (the exact extent and means of integration are yet to be determined during development and implementation). Its essential interactive visualisation dashboarding functionalities are to provide as accurate and up-to-date monitoring information on the detected congestions and resulting delays and deviations compared to the initially planned routes (per requirements such as SR-014, SR-065, and others), as well as proactive outputs from the underlying analytics and predictions, including also alerts and recommendations for actionable support to the decision-making processes (SR-034, to SR-065). It will be implemented as a web or hybrid application designed over a common state-of-the-art relevant architectural pattern (like MVC), and with optional standalone UI widgets/controls considered for integration (embedding) into existing external tools or applications, if found optimal.

The used core essential hardware devices to be connected and integrated are on the **IoT Layer** on the right of the diagram in Figure 3. The components in the listed main groups are specified in additional detail in the next following section, divided into hardware and software, and with mapping to the core provided functionalities crucial for Project Objectives and KPIs.

The data exchange and workflows between the components of the system will be orchestrated on the service middleware through an **API Gateway** baseline architectural pattern for orchestration, based on REST communication. If needed, it can be extended in the future with Message Queues (MQ)

which would also enable multiple nodes of same services to compete as queue consumers (Gateway would serve as a producer), thus facilitating horizontal scale-up.

The components and modules represented with a dashed outline on the diagram (and the corresponding dashed data/communication flow arrows) are optional, and their inclusion in the architecture and implementation depends on the specific details currently still not determined and under consideration, like supported connectivity or interfacing of the hardware devices that are to be integrated, or common platform components shared across the RDP and RWP supporting services that are yet to be defined in full detail during the development. The presented planned granular decomposition of code modules and packages of the system core across the mid- and front-end tiers is structured per generalized main types of functionalities or analytic methods that cater to the user needs, goals and requirements documented in the previous chapter, and also based on the structure and modularity of the existing and parallelly developed solutions and modules in the ZEN portfolio, aiming for optimal adaptability, scalability and minimized cost in exploitation, including beyond the Project.

3.1.2 RDP service components description and specification

3.1.2.1. Hardware components

The needed essential hardware components for the RDP service are mainly vehicle-mounted sensory devices for in-situ monitoring and tracking, and the flying drone – aerial vehicle itself with all sensing and monitoring and onboard processing equipment mounted on it, as depicted on the “**IoT Layer**” on the top right of Figure 3 above.

A state-of-the-art safe, robust, extensible and configurable UAV, able to fulfil the related relevant requirements specified above (SR-008, SR-014) and the Project ambition, equipped for visual/optical recognition (high-resolution camera) and the supporting ranging LIDAR sensing for precise distance measurements, and with the capability of onboard execution of advanced detection algorithms, will be utilised to acquire and provide on-demand accurate real-time data on congestions and parking space availability. It will also leverage on the OS-NMA authentication protocol, a key security feature of EGNSS ensuring data integrity, reliability and tamper-proof robustness, as described in more detail under 3.1.2.2.4 further below. This technology not only enhances the efficiency of transport and logistics management but also supports the broader objectives of safety, compliance, economic efficiency, and environmental sustainability.

In-truck GNSS tracking devices are leveraged to improve the accuracy of vehicle tracking and fleet management, transmitting accurate location data and telemetry information to the fleet management system through the data acquisition, validation and consolidation service APIs in the core middle tier.

Intermediate edge-device computing boards or IoT cloud/edge nodes or hubs involved are represented on the “IoT Layer” on the right of Figure 3 above, with the likely candidates being a common edge computing device (like Nvidia Jetson) featuring sufficient performance for processing necessities. Data acquisition through optional 3rd-party cloud APIs of specific hardware vendor(s), rendered with dashed borders on the bottom right of the diagram, is planned in case the data from any sensor device is exposed by the manufacturer only this way. When the complete landscape of hardware to be used is finalized, it will also be definitely decided on including these architecture options or not.

3.1.2.1.1. EGNSS In-vehicle Tracking

The determination of the positions of the trucks is carried out with a positioning accuracy of under 2.5m CEP, by the installed GNSS-supporting robust and feature-rich AT tracking device from Astra Telematics⁷, shown in detail on Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Astra Telematics AT242 GNSS tracking device installed in RDP demonstrator trucks

The specifications of the AT242 EGNSS tracking device are given in the Table 6 below.

Table 6 – Specifications of the AT242 EGNSS

Type	Feature	Value	System/User Req.
Positioning	Accuracy	< 2.5m CEP @ -130dBm	SR-014
	L1/B1 Receiver	GPS L1 C/A, GLONASS L1, GNSS supporting all available satellite systems, BeiDou B1 C/A	SR-014, SR-059
Specific EGNSS positioning support (GNSS precision)	GNSS Antenna	Internal 25mm ceramic patch	SR-014
	GNSS Receiver	u-blox EVA-M8M or Quectel LG77L (both with SBAS support)	SR-014, SR-059

⁷ <https://astratelematics.com/product/at242-ip67-4g-lte-gsm-gnss-ble-tracking-device>

augmented by EGNOS as a specific SBAS service)	GNSS Chipset	Mediatek MT3333 (supporting SBAS ranging from WAAS, EGNOS, GAGAN and MSAS)	SR-014, SR-059
Connectivity	Mobile/Cellular IoT	4G LTE Cat 1	SR-014, SR-059
	Ports/Connectors	4 x digital pull-up inputs 2 x digital pull-down inputs 5 x digital outputs, 60V, 0.5A Maximum (MOSFET open drain) CANBus / FMS 2.0 / OBD2 2 x RS232 serial port 2 x ADC inputs (0–5V and 0-15V) 3.3V Auxiliary Output 4.5V Auxiliary Output	SR-014
	Bluetooth	BLE 4.2	SR-014 SR-059
Operating performance	Battery & life	3.7V, 510mAh 9 hours continuous operation 12 days operation in low-power mode with hourly updates 20 days operation in low-power mode with daily updates	SR-033
	Memory & report storage	1024k on-board non-volatile flash memory 6000 reports	SR-033
	Operative temperature range	-20 to +85°C (battery charging suspended at higher temperatures)	SR-033
	Ingress Protection	IP67 (practically waterproof and dustproof)	SR-033

3.1.2.1.2. The UAV for in-situ detection and monitoring

The specification of the selected robust industry-benchmark UAV utilized for on-demand most accurate and reliable in-situ detection and verification of road congestions and parking places availability in RDP, supporting OS-NMA in authentication, is provided in the table below, with detailed onboard sensing and processing payload equipment (optical RGB camera, LIDAR) and their features:

Figure 5. DJI Matrice M350 RTK UAV, the enterprise flagship DJI model (DJI, 2024)

Table 7 - The main features of SPATRA RDP monitoring and detection UAV

Type	Feature	Value	System/User Req.
Aircraft			UR-114
Data	Dimensions (unfolded, excl. propellers)	810 mm × 670 mm × 430 mm (L × W × H)	–
	Dimensions (folded)	430 mm × 420 mm × 430 mm (L × W × H)	–
	Diagonal Wheelbase	668 mm	–
	Weight (excl. batteries)	3770 g (approx.)	–
	Weight (incl. two batteries)	6470 g (approx.)	–

Single Gimbal Damper's Max Payload	960 g	—
Max Takeoff Weight	9200 g	—
Operation Frequency	2.4000 GHz to 2.4835 GHz (Europe)	—
Transmitter Power (EIRP)	2.4 GHz CE (Europe): < 20 dBm	v
Hovering Accuracy (windless or breezy)	Vertical: ± 0.1 m (Vision System enabled); ± 0.5 m (N-mode with GNSS); ± 0.1 m (RTK) Horizontal: ± 0.3 m (Vision System enabled); ± 1.5 m (N-mode with GNSS); ± 0.1 m (RTK)	v
RTK Positioning Accuracy (fixed RTK enabled)	1 cm + 1 ppm (horizontal) 1.5 cm + 1 ppm (vertical)	SR-014
Max Angular Velocity	Pitch: 300°/sec.; Yaw: 100°/sec.	—
Max Pitch Angle	30° (N-mode and Forward Vision System enabled: 25°)	—
Max Ascent/Descent Speed	6 m/s, 5 m/s	—
Max Tilt Descent Speed	7 m/s	—
Max Horizontal Speed	23 m/s	—
Max Service Ceiling Above Sea Level (without other payload)	5000 m (with 2110s propellers & take-off weight ≤ 7.4 kg) 7000 m (with 2112 High-Altitude Low-Noise propellers & take-off weight ≤ 7.2 kg)	—

	Max Wind Resistance	12 m/s	–
	Max Flight Time	55 min (8 m/s, without payloads, windless)	–
	Supported DJI Gimbals	Zenmuse H20, Zenmuse H20T, Zenmuse H20N, Zenmuse P1, and Zenmuse L1	–
	Supported Gimbal Configurations	Single downward gimbal, Single upward gimbal, Dual downward gimbals, Single downward gimbal + single upward gimbal, Dual downward gimbals + single upward gimbal	–
	Third-Party Payload	Only certified payloads (DJI Payload SDK)	SR-033
	Ingress Protection Rating	IP55	–
	GNSS	GPS + Galileo + BeiDou + GLONASS	–
	Operating Temperature	-20° C to 50° C	–
Aircraft's Onboard Vision Systems			
Data	Obstacle Sensing Range	Forward/Backward/Left/Right: 0.7-40 m Upward/Downward: 0.6-30 m	–
	FOV	Forward/Backward/Downward: 65° (horizontal), 50° (vertical) Left/Right/Upward: 75° (horizontal), 60° (vertical)	–
	Operating Environment	Surfaces with clear patterns and adequate lighting (> 15 lux)	–
Aircraft's Onboard Infrared Sensing Systems			
Data	Obstacle Sensing Range	0.1 m to 8 m	–
	FOV	30° (±15°)	–

	Operating Environment	Large, diffuse, and reflective obstacles (reflectivity > 10%)	–
O3 Enterprise Transmission			
Data	Operating Frequency	2.4000 GHz to 2.4835 GHz (Europe)	–
	Max Transmission Distance (unobstructed, free of interference)	8 km CE (Europe)	SR-014
	Max Transmission Distance (with interference)	<p>Low Interference and Obstructed by Buildings: approx. 0-0.5 km</p> <p>Low Interference and Obstructed by Trees: approx. 0.5-3 km</p> <p>Strong Interference and Unobstructed: urban landscape, approx. 1.5-3 km</p> <p>Medium Interference and Unobstructed: suburban landscape, approx. 3-9 km</p> <p>Low Interference and Unobstructed: suburb/seaside, approx. 9-20 km</p>	SR-014
	Transmitter Power (EIRP)	2.4 GHz CE (Europe): < 20 dBm	–
LiDAR Gimbal – Zenmuse L1			UR-109 UR-114 SR-059
Data	Dimensions	152 mm × 110 mm × 169 mm (L × W × H)	–
	Weight	930±10 g	–
	Power	Typical: 30 W; Max: 60 W	–
	IP Rating	IP54	–
	Operating Temperature Range	-20° to 50° C 0° to 50° C (when using RGB mapping camera)	–

Storage Temperature Range	-20° to 60° C	–
Detection Range	450 m @ 80% reflectivity, 0 klx 190 m @ 10% reflectivity, 100 klx	–
Point Rate	Single return: max. 240,000 pts/s Multiple return: max. 480,000 pts/s	–
System Accuracy (RMS 1σ)	Horizontal: 10 cm @ 50 m Vertical: 5 cm @ 50 m	–
Real-time Point Cloud Coloring Modes	Reflectivity, Height, Distance, RGB	–
Ranging Accuracy (RMS 1σ)	3 cm @ 100 m	–
Maximum Returns Supported	3	–
Scan Modes	Non-repetitive scanning pattern, Repetitive scanning pattern	–
FOV	Non-repetitive scanning pattern: 70.4° (horizontal) × 77.2° (vertical) Repetitive scanning pattern: 70.4° (horizontal) × 4.5° (vertical)	–
Laser Safety	Class 1 (IEC 60825-1:2014) (Eye Safety)	–
INS Integrated IMU Update Frequency	200 Hz	–
INS Integrated Accelerometer Range	±8 g	–
INS Integrated Angular Velocity Meter Range	±2000 dps	–

INS Yaw Accuracy (RMS 1 σ)	Real-time: 0.3° Post-processing: 0.15°	–
INS Pitch / Roll Accuracy (RMS 1 σ)	Real-time: 0.05°, Post-processing: 0.025°	–
Auxiliary Positioning Vision Sensor	Resolution: 1280×960, FOV: 95°	SR-059
Integrated RGB Sensor Size	2.54 cm	–
Integrated RGB Effective Pixels	20MP	–
Integrated RGB Photo Size	5472×3078 (16:9); 4864×3648 (4:3); 5472×3648 (3:2)	–
Integrated RGB Focal Length	8.8 mm / 24 mm (Equivalent)	–
Integrated RGB Shutter Speed	Mechanical Shutter Speed: 1/2000 - 8 s Electronic Shutter Speed: 1/8000 - 8 s	–
Integrated RGB ISO	Video: 100 – 3200 (Auto), 100 – 6400 (Manual) Photo: 100 - 3200 (Auto), 100 - 12800 (Manual)	–
Integrated RGB Aperture Range	f/2.8 - f/11	–
Integrated RGB Video Resolution	H.264, 4K: 3840×2160 30p	–
Gimbal Stabilization System	3-axis (tilt, roll, pan)	–
Gimbal Angular Vibration Range	0.01°	–
Gimbal Mechanical Range	Tilt: -120° to +30°; Pan: ±320°	–

	Gimbal Operation Modes	Follow/Free/Re-center	–
RGB Camera System Gimbal – Zennuse H20			SR-059
Data	Dimensions	150mm × 114mm × 151mm	–
	Weight	678±5 g	–
	Ingress Protection Rating	IP44	–
	Operating Temperature	-20° to 50° C	–
	Sensor	Zoom Camera: 1/1.7" CMOS, 20 MP Wide-angle Camera: 1/2.3" CMOS, 12 MP	–
	Lens	Zoom Camera: DFOV: 66.6°-4° Focal length: 6.83-119.94 mm (equivalent: 31.7-556.2 mm) Aperture: f/2.8-f/11 (normal), f/1.6-f/11 (night scene) Focus: 1 m to ∞ (wide), 8 m to ∞ (telephoto) Wide-angle Camera: DFOV: 82.9° Focal length: 4.5 mm (equivalent: 24 mm) Aperture: f/2.8 Focus: 1 m to ∞	–
	Focus Mode	Zoom Camera: MF/AF-C/AF-S Wide-angle Camera: N/A	–
	Exposure Mode	Zoom Camera: Auto, Manual Wide-angle Camera: Auto	–
	Exposure Compensation	Zoom Camera: ±3.0 (1/3 increments) Wide-angle Camera: ±3.0 (1/3 increments)	–
	Metering Mode	Zoom Camera: Spot metering, Center-weighted metering	–

		Wide-angle Camera: Spot metering, Center-weighted metering	
AE LOCK		Zoom Camera: Supported Wide-angle Camera: Supported	–
Electronic Shutter Speed		Zoom Camera: 1 ~ 1/8000 s Wide-angle Camera: 1 ~ 1/8000 s	–
ISO Range		Zoom Camera: 100 – 25600 (video), 100 – 25600 (photo) Wide-angle Camera: 100 – 25600 (video), 100 – 25600 (photo)	–
Video Resolution		Zoom Camera: 3840x2160@30fps, 1920x1080@30fps Wide-angle Camera: 1920x1080@30fps	–
Photo Size		Zoom Camera: 5184 × 3888 Wide-angle Camera: 4056 x 3040	–
Laser Rangefinder Safety		Class 1M (IEC 60825-1:2014)	–
Laser Rangefinder Wavelength		905 nm	–
Laser Rangefinder Measurement range		3-1200 m (to a vertical surface with ≥ 12 m diameter and 20% reflection rate)	–
Laser Rangefinder Measurement accuracy		$\pm (0.2 \text{ m} + D \times 0.15\%)$ D is the distance to a vertical surface	–
Laser Rangefinder Accessible Emission Limit (AEL)		327.84 nJ	–
Laser Rangefinder Reference Aperture		18mm length, 18mm width (20.3mm diameter if equivalent to circular)	–
Laser Rangefinder Max Pulse Emission		65.6 W	–

	Power Within 5 Nanoseconds		
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On-board processing hardware

A “companion” computing board, installed on the UAV, will be used for processing sensor data and running detection algorithms in the optimal targeted real-time process (along with a communication module facilitating data transmission to the server back end, and the reception of commands). It will be integrated with the drone via the integration/development resources available and exposed by the vendor (mainly the DJI “Payload” SDK and the available ports), and should support the execution of the computer vision and recognition models (like the YOLO model specified in 3.1.2.2.4 below) in nearest possible to real-time on the drone, as well as of preprocessing and data fusion techniques used to combine visual data from cameras and depth data from LIDAR.

Additionally, to the commonly CPU-based such add-on companion boards or computing modules available and compatible with the used UAV, a more powerful GPU-accelerated computing option - Nvidia Jetson platform⁸ (Jetson Xavier or Jetson Nano) has also been evaluated by the project partners, as the current practically industrially applicable cutting-edge platform setting a new global standard in GPU-assisted running of AI on mobile/edge embedded devices for onboard processing. It is a ready reserve option to handle eventual increasing complexity of the deep learning algorithms for detection or demanding data fusion and parallel pre-processing techniques for reducing noise (Kalman and particle filters), temporal regularization (dynamic time warping), and improving overall detection reliability (at some additional cost, currently estimated at up to 500€ higher than a CPU-based board), if necessary, or in more complex and demanding exploitation scale-up scenarios beyond the scope of the Project.

3.1.2.2. Software components per provided key core features

As shown on Figure 3 above, the various core system packages and modules across the service middleware, analytics and front-end tiers, integrated together provide and support the crucial RDP domain functionalities in the manner specified in the subsections following below, including the descriptions and reporting the outcomes how some additional advanced or alternative features and methods have been tested and evaluated.

3.1.2.2.1 SENTINEL-2 Truck detection

⁸ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-eu/autonomous-machines/embedded-systems>

Monitoring freight vehicles in traffic using machine learning for detection of trucks in high-resolution satellite images has been successfully proven as a concept^{9,10}, and should be useful for the prediction of average daily rates, when the high-resolution images eventually become openly available in finer temporal resolution as well. The essential preprocessing and necessary background feature extraction steps have been performed – roads and the supporting infrastructure extracted from the satellite images using OpenStreetMap road data to obtain GeoPolygons or GeoDataFrames, rasterizing them to get a binary mask in scale, and then multiplying it with the satellite image to extract only roads (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Original source satellite image of the Horgoš Serbia-Hungary border crossing (left), and the resulting mask with extracted roads and auxiliary infrastructure (right)

9 Lynn H. Kaack, George H. Chen, and M. Granger Morgan. 2019. Truck traffic monitoring with satellite images. In Proceedings of the 2nd ACM SIGCAS Conference on Computing and Sustainable Societies (COMPASS '19). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 155–164. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3314344.3332480>

10 Abraham, L. and Sasikumar, M.: Vehicle Detection and Classification from High Resolution Satellite Images, ISPRS Ann. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., II-1, 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsannals-II-1-1-2014>, 2014.

Figure 7. Long congestion line of trucks (enlarged on the left) traced from the image with superimposed road infrastructure mask

The methods in the modules for Image segmentation, multiplication & enhancement (on the Analytics core layer) and for Preprocessing/Augmentation (in the Service Middleware, Figure 3 architecture diagram above) are performing image preprocessing and preparatory steps like this. The FoI Detection analytics package then performs the trucks detection on the pre-processed results. But currently still a major limitation for the usability of fine-resolution images, like available from the SENTINEL-2 mission in 10 to 50m, is that continuous images monitoring over a same single point/area (like a border crossing) can at present be obtained only once in every 4-5 days, not feasible for even close to the needed pervasive near-real-time freight traffic frequency monitoring (and the finest available spatial resolution of 10m per pixel also being practically problematic to distinguish anything across the road width and enabling only the detection of lengths of trucks with trailers, exceeding 10m, not of all relevant truck types).

The FoI for SPATRA RDP that have by now turned out feasible and with some certain usability for direct recognition from SENTINEL-2 images are the long queue lines of trucks at the very border crossing, commonly extending kilometres in length and persisting for days (Figure 7).

In practical terms this very limited applicability of direct detection and recognition from SENTINEL-2 images had suggested that indirect and inference methods, as well as supporting exploitable data from additional alternative sources, would have to be explored, aligned with the general Task 2.2 research direction of considering interfaces to additional, upcoming, or new EO data sources and data products.

We have therefore tried and evaluated other complementary methods for enhancing the quality and adequacy of the obtained raw satellite images for detection, and for correlating with data from additional alternative available sources. Such methods and models shown promising in this preliminary evaluation remain candidates for implementation in the package for images preprocessing and enhancements (segmentation, multiplication, edge detection) in the analytics tier, and experimentation with some other also tested methods and techniques eventually ultimately found not viable, are reported below as well.

SENTINEL-2 multispectral temporal offset-based method for moving objects detection

This recent method (2022) presented by Fisser et al.¹¹ exploits a temporal sensing offset of the SENTINEL-2 multispectral instrument, causing recognizably spatially and spectrally distorted signatures of moving objects (trucks). The satellite instrument captures the blue, green and red light from large moving objects at slightly different times, and combining these light channels reveals (a very likely presence of) a moving truck seen as a rainbow-like signatures sequence of pixels against the road as a background (Figure 8).

The method (almost a clever hack) successfully distinguishes moving trucks, even in borderline low resolution, from reflected solar electromagnetic radiation in separate bands captured on the images, but that still does not overcome the main challenge of having too sparse data points in time for systematic continuous monitoring of pinpointed area to be feasible. It is also not guaranteed to remain applicable in years to come, with the expected updates of SENTINEL-2 mission satellites and instrumentation.

Figure 8. Moving truck footprint in satellite images leaving a distinctive rainbow-like pattern in separated red, green and blue channels

3.1.2.2.2 Additional and alternative supporting detection methods from EO sources

Super-resolution

This image enhancement approach has been used to improve and upscale the spatial resolution of SENTINEL-2 images from best native 10m per pixel up to 2.5 m per pixel with deep learning models based on known terrain and road network features¹² (Figure 9). It is an applicable approach for more

11 Fisser, H.; Khorsandi, E.; Wegmann, M.; Baier, F. Detecting Moving Trucks on Roads Using Sentinel-2 Data. *Remote Sens.* **2022**, *14*, 1595. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14071595>

12 Jia, Y.; Zhang, X.; Xiang, R.; Ge, Y. Super-Resolution Rural Road Extraction from Sentinel-2 Imagery Using a Spatial Relationship-Informed Network. *Remote Sens.* **2023**, *15*, 4193. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15174193>

accurate detection of parking places availability and occupancy (with open-source tools¹³ and community model support at disposal¹⁴), with the resolution-improving model possible to train on Google Earth data as ground truth - but again only if and when the source satellite data become available in finer temporal intra-daily resolution, as the method cannot reconstruct the parked trucks that are not visible in the original source images.

Figure 9. An example of a satellite image enhancement applying a super-resolution method (right)

Additional higher-resolution image sources

Some specialized online sources like the Truck Parking Europe web application for search and booking of parking spaces - <https://app.truckparkingeurope.com> - features detailed images of most of the truck parking areas (Figure 10) across Europe in higher resolution than available (or will be in near future) from SENTINEL, with clearly discernible individual parking places lines and truck contours, notably different from other vehicle types on the images.

13 SR4RS open-source tool for super resolution, <https://github.com/remicres/sr4rs>

14 Example using GAN - <https://github.com/purijs/satellite-superresolution>
SPATRA GA 101129658 D 2.1

Figure 10. Zoomed-in parking places and parked trucks images from truckparkingeurope.com

These additional supporting source images are also not directly useful for monitoring and detection but may be for establishing baseline ground truth and referent temporal trends of parking space occupancy, as well as for model training and validation.

Other satellite imaging sources also offer images in visible and multispectral higher resolution than SENTINEL-2, some of which even in very high resolution (VHR) under 5m per pixel and with multiple revisit times per day supported for any location globally, like the WorldView-3 (sub-meter spatial resolution data already from WorldView-2 have been successfully used in detection of vehicles, positions and movement¹⁵), PlanetScope or Pléiades Neo. These sources are mostly

¹⁵ B.Salehi, Y. Zhang and M. Zhong (2012), "Object-based moving vehicle extraction from WorldView-2 imagery", American Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing Annual Conference 2012, ASPRS 2012. 470-476.

commercial and charge the data access or provision, but are also participating in the ESA's Third-Party Missions programme¹⁶, with ESA extensively promoting and supporting the availability of their data for research and development purposes. This way some of their data products can in principle be obtained free of charge for research and exploration purposes, upon submitted application with the relevant research/project description, and the consequent assessment and approval by the ESA and the data/product owner taking up to 6 weeks. Developments in this general applied innovation direction of next-generation EO based on widely available super-resolution (SR) data are progressing swiftly¹⁷, and are being closely followed by the SPATRA development teams.

Indirect inference from SENTINEL-5P air pollution data and SENTINEL-3 LST

The TROPOMI (TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument) sensor¹⁸ mounted on the Copernicus SENTINEL-5P satellite monitors a wide range of particulate aerosol and gaseous air pollutants (smoke and dust particles, CO, NO₂, SO₂, O₃, CH₄, formaldehydes...) and renders their spatial concentration distributions in colour-coded "heatmap" layers over the geomap (Figure 11), integrated for querying, processing and retrieval through various platforms and methods, including Google Earth Engine (GEE). The temporal resolution of these data is notably finer than for the SENTINEL-2 images, but still just one snapshot per day available for a single detailed location, while the spatial resolution is notably coarser (down to 1km per pixel). They have though been used for inferring traffic frequency/density in microclimate variations or intra-urban smaller areas¹⁹, in combination with temperature from SENTINEL-3 and other IoT-sourced measurements^{20,21}.

The usefulness of this data for indirect inference of congestions in areas of interest is even further limited by

- occasional occlusions of the ground by the clouds or atmospheric obstacles making the pollutant concentration measurements impossible and consequently "holes" in the data, and most of all by
- the specifics of the RDP use case itself, like the fact that many trucks waiting in a congestion line still keep their engines off and not running most of the time, and the congestions can therefore often cause no measurable increase in overall local air pollution resulting from exhaust gasses, leading to a substantial number of false negatives in detection.

¹⁶ <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/international-collaboration-summarising-esas-third-party-missions>

¹⁷ <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/meet-the-future-of-earth-observation-super-resolution-data> (accessed July 17th, 2024)

¹⁸ <https://www.tropomi.eu>

¹⁹ M. Kazemi Garajeh, G. Laneve et al. "Monitoring Trends of CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃ Pollutants Using Time-Series Sentinel-5 Images Based on Google Earth Engine", *Pollutants* 2023, 3, 255-279. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pollutants3020019>

²⁰ E. Husni, G.A. Prayoga et al. "Microclimate investigation of vehicular traffic on the urban heat island through IoT-Based device", *Heliyon* 2022 Nov 17;8(11):e11739. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11739

²¹ X. Li, G. Zhang et al. "Step-By-Step Downscaling of Land Surface Temperature Considering Urban Spatial Morphological Parameters", *Remote Sens.* 2022, 14, 3038. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14133038>

Figure 11. Example of SENTINEL-5P air pollution data - UV aerosol index distribution over the Balkans

Inferencing from these data sources could thus at best be an optional supporting method with low and limited applicable reliability, mainly for detected positives (increased air pollution and/or LST in congestion-suspected areas).

3.1.2.2.3 EGNSS truck localization and telemetry tracking

This use of EGNSS and Copernicus is the actual cornerstone of applicable real-time monitoring of road traffic flow in RDP leveraging EO services (directly fulfilling SR-003), improving the accuracy of vehicle tracking and fleet management and providing the key inputs for prediction of congestions and ETA delays in logistics network flows, and deeper trends analysis of time-series data (SR-008) extending also into the past, before the SPATRA start and temporal scope. The method is though limited only to vehicles under full control and access to install the GNSS trackers, provided by the Demonstrator UC logistics partner, but in case of Nelt this can in production service exploitation also include installation of GNSS trackers in the vehicles of their other subcontracted carriers, adding up to extensive road network coverage throughout the region.

A suitable accurate and robust AT242 GNSS tracking device available on the market has been selected (hardware specification provided in 3.1.2.1.1), convenient for installation and integration, and the initial data transmission pipeline to the RDP Core cloud has been made and tested in the scope of the relevant Task 3.4. Sample data from the tracker have been acquired by the *Data Consolidation & Validation* service methods through the API Gateway, parsed from the native format into standard GeoJSON, and stored as trajectories containing time-series of vehicle positions (Figure 12) (and optional additional telemetry data like momentary vehicle speed, engine rpm, temperature, or others) in the central *Data Store*, at disposal for further subsequent usage in direct detection of congestions, propagation to alerting/notifications module, improving predictions, etc.

Figure 12. Sample of vehicle trajectories acquired from a GNSS tracker throughout a given timeline

3.1.2.2.4 Parking drone detection algorithm

Truck parking has become a significant logistical challenge due to the increasing number of trucks on the road and limited parking spaces. Ensuring the security and optimal use of these parking spaces is critical. This section outlines a drone-based detection algorithm integrated with OS-NMA (Open Service Navigation Message Authentication) for secure and accurate truck parking management.

OS-NMA Authentication

OS-NMA is a security feature of the Galileo satellite navigation system, designed to provide cryptographic authentication of navigation messages. This ensures that the data received by the drone's navigation system is authentic and has not been tampered with. OS-NMA is crucial for applications requiring high integrity and reliability, such as drone-based truck parking detection.

The working principle of OS-NMA involves the transmission of navigation messages by Galileo satellites, which include cryptographic signatures. The public keys required to verify these signatures are pre-distributed to the drone's navigation system. The drone's onboard system uses these public keys to verify the authenticity of the received navigation messages in real-time, ensuring the integrity and authenticity of the information.

The benefits of OS-NMA in truck parking detection are manifold. Firstly, it prevents spoofing, ensuring that the drone's navigation data is not tampered with, thereby preventing potential spoofing

attacks. Secondly, it enhances security by providing an additional layer of protection, which is critical for applications in public and high-value areas. Lastly, it improves reliability by ensuring the dependable operation of the drone, minimizing the risk of incorrect parking detection.

Algorithm Description

The drone detection algorithm for truck parking involves multiple steps, from initial detection to final reporting. The algorithm leverages the OS-NMA authenticated navigation data to perform precise and secure operations.

The execution subsystem relies on several crucial integrated hardware components specified above, the drone platform equipped with high-resolution cameras, LIDAR sensors, and a Galileo receiver with OS-NMA capability. A central processing unit (CPU) on the onboard companion computer is used for processing sensor data and running detection algorithms, while a communication module facilitates data transmission to a central server and reception of commands.

The algorithm initiates with the drone's systems startup, which includes the authentication of the received navigation data using OS-NMA. A pre-flight check ensures all sensors and systems are operational. The drone then conducts an aerial survey of the truck parking area, capturing high-resolution optical RGB images and measured depth/distance data.

Data processing involves several steps. Image processing techniques are used to detect and classify trucks in the parking area. This includes feature extraction to identify truck features such as size, shape, and color, subsequently used as inputs to the main assets detection algorithm based on well-established Region Proposal Networks, like YOLO (You Only Look Once) or SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) for real-time detection. LIDAR analysis complements image processing by providing depth information to enhance detection accuracy. The next phase involves parking space analysis. The system determines which parking spaces are occupied or available and identifies any irregularities or unauthorized parking through pattern recognition, by confirming any trucks stationed at designated parking spots (Figure 13). Throughout the process, continuous OS-NMA verification is conducted to ensure ongoing integrity, and an alert system triggers alerts if any anomaly in navigation data is detected.

Figure 13. Parking area availability analysis implemented on the SPATRA RDP drone subsystem

In the reporting and communication phase, the processed data is transmitted to a central server back end for further analysis and record-keeping. This subsystem should be able to provide real-time parking status updates to the logistics/transport management system, dispatchers/operators or planners/coordinators (even customer care department staff as end-users of both these and congestion detection features, as stated explicitly by the involved logistics companies at the held stakeholder consultation workshops), or as notifications or alerts relayed directly to the truck drivers.

Finally, the drone ensures a safe return to the designated landing zone, powering down systems safely after completing the operation.

3.1.2.2.5 Drone-based Congestion detection algorithm

The drone-based truck congestion detection algorithm involves a sequence of steps designed to accurately monitor and analyse truck congestion near borders. Initially, the drone captures high-resolution images of the area using a multi-rotor drone equipped with a high-resolution camera and additional sensors such as LIDAR and infrared (or optionally/additionally ultrasonic sensors). These sensors ensure precise distance measurements, crucial for reconstructing a volumetric representation of the targeted area, and the subsequent analysis (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Congestion detection implemented on the SPATRA RDP drone subsystem

Once the images and measurements from the sensors are captured (associated to the exact positioning of the drone), merging and preprocessing steps are applied to derive/reconstruct the comprehensive and seamless view of the monitored area (combining stitched or overlapped RGB images, depth, IMU, and Galileo measurement data), and enhance the imaging quality if needed (using noise reduction or other filters to remove unwanted artifacts impeding detection).

The core of the algorithm lies in its object detection capabilities. Utilizing advanced techniques like the YOLO (You Only Look Once) framework, the algorithm can detect and classify trucks in real-time. YOLO is renowned for its balance of speed and accuracy, making it highly suitable for dynamic environments. Additionally, novel enhancements such as GGT-YOLO will be considered, integrating GhostNet and Transformer technologies to improve feature extraction, especially for small or occluded objects.

Such techniques not only boost detection accuracy but also reduce computational costs by replacing complex convolution operations with more efficient linear transformations.

Following the object detection, the algorithm employs the volumetric environment representation data generated from LIDAR or ultrasonic sensor measurements to determine the distances between the detected trucks and the border. This precise distance measurement is pivotal for understanding the spatial arrangement and movement of the trucks.

The final phase involves a thorough congestion analysis. Here, the algorithm extracts key features such as the number of trucks and their distribution across the monitored area. It calculates distances between the trucks and the border to develop congestion metrics, which quantify the level of congestion based on truck density and average distance from the border.

This entire process is implemented using robust industry-supported programming tools and widespread deep learning frameworks such as TensorFlow or PyTorch. The algorithm's effectiveness is validated through extensive testing with diverse datasets to ensure accuracy under various lighting conditions. By integrating these advanced detection techniques and robust preprocessing steps, the algorithm provides real-time insights into truck congestion near borders, aiding in efficient traffic management and border control operations.

3.1.2.2.6 Extended Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) calculation

The ETA calculation component extends the common methods based on location and distance to destination with additional monitored and predicted data on border congestions and delays, various considered dynamic factors from diverse data sources influencing congestion mentioned in the previous sections above, to ultimately deliver more precise, comprehensive and reliable extended total ETAs (SR-014, SR-065).

Additionally to the satellite-sourced images, time-series of EGNSS positioning data of trucks in congestion lines, and on-demand images taken by a drone or land cameras to verify or provide detailed information on truck waiting lines at the border (determining the precise end of the queue), the attainable parameters also potentially influencing congestions are:

- open weather data – inclement or extremely hot weather can significantly impact not only truck speeds on the route but also the efficiency of border operations, leading to delays.
- extraordinary or periodic events or procedures known to cause delays, such as customs shift changes, introduction of new or changed administrative procedures, and other notable occurrences, to be supported to enter and integrated into the system. These events are known to create bottlenecks and extend waiting times.
- general seasonal patterns of increased traffic flows and bottlenecks at the border crossings (working days vs weekends, holiday periods or seasons, etc.).

Substantial challenge remains the dynamic determination of relative importance and influence how and to what exact extent each of the listed parameters and factors (or main features extracted from the raw data) contributes to the overall calculated ETA. Ensemble algorithm methods are intended to be employed for this in a sort of “meta-learning” approach, evaluating various suitable classifiers (AdaBoost, Naïve Bayes and Bayesian networks, SVM, random forests, decision trees, k-Nearest Neighbours) in cross-validation and against ETA assessment/prediction accuracy metrics, to be able to adaptively assign feature/factor importance scores quantifying their influence on the resulting complete extended ETA. This can be further complemented by a sensitivity analysis evaluating the impact of different features by experimentally excluding individual ones from the assessment, and visual analysis of the relative effects through techniques like Partial Dependence or Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) Plots.

3.1.2.2.7 RDP monitoring application

The application for comprehensive monitoring of traffic flows and predicting for logistics is the main planned **Front-end** tier tool to be provided to the end users, with its web-based graphical user interface designed to meet the key expressed user needs and requirements specified in tables in sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3 above (serving as the primary means for delivering to the users the RDP service outputs and interactivity required in key system requirements pertaining to the Web GUI, such as SR-002, SR-003, SR-004, SR-005, or SR-007 to SR-009).

The application UI will handle the user (http) requests to invoke methods from the dedicated **Applicative & data provision** back-end service middleware package, which in turn retrieves the queried results from the relevant datasets in the **Data Store** via the generic infrastructural **Persistence** services (Figure 3). It will then generate http response(s) from obtained results, using the UI states and data controlling logic organized in a “separation of concern” architectural pattern like *MVC*, and present them back to the user.

In the opposite-directed data flow propagating from the back end to the front end without request, the **Alerting/Notification and Scheduling** module, running periodic or domain-logic-triggered batch jobs, will generate relevant proactive push objects with actionable or anomalous data and content for the end users, and propagate them as corresponding http(s) responses to the web GUI, or as optional direct messages or e-mails.

The front-end will be built using a robust state-of-the-art Javascript web development framework like React or Vue, integrating spatial map libraries like Leaflet, request chaining and error handling ones like Axios.js, and others as necessary.

GUI mock-ups

Top-level initial combined spatio-temporal interactive data overview features an intuitive geomap with overlaid and/or connected monitoring data presented in the same view, through tabular and diagram UI controls as illustrated in the Figure 15.

Figure 15. Main overview page mock-up of the RDP monitoring application, with combined geomap and tabular and temporal diagram connected parallel contextual data visualizations

Figure 16. Example of colour-coded alert and notification icons denoting parking ground occupancy levels graphically plotted along the route (itself in colour-coded line sections signifying congestions severity on the scale from red through yellow to blue) and in its vicinity

They present relevant monitoring data and detection/prediction outputs in the spatio-temporal context of the selected areas and features of interest on the map, as additional connected tabular and/or chart visualizations, also covering the provision of essential ad-hoc operative reporting.

Alerts and status notifications can also be displayed immediately on the map main overview content panel, rendered as icons overlaid on the map, or on a dedicated panel as illustrated on the Figure 16.

Further drill-down UI workflows are to branch from the main overview page to more focused FoI assets overviews plotted on the map, like a fleet of trucks with current vehicle positions and statuses (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Fleet state overview

Ad-hoc and historical detailed exportable reports are to provide the users with detailed and granular historical and ad-hoc reporting (example on Figure 18) on the monitored assets (vehicles, slots) and detected events (all identified and predicted congestions, delays, and their effects on the route ETAs, planning and actual execution), possible to export and download in common data formats (delimited text, Excel, JSON...).

Figure 18. Example of an ad-hoc report

Extensive configurability is also an important highly desirable infrastructural requirement, particularly for scalability and sustainability in exploitation beyond the Project, and it will extend to essential hardware integration, enabling to register/de-register or elementarily reconfigure additional

data sources and devices installed or linked to vehicles and other assets (FoI), and PoI locations, as shown on Figure 19.

Field	Create device	Edit device
Device type	Select device type	Teltonika FM4200
Registration	Select registration	Select registration
IMEI		352848029698897
MSISDN		665675759
Active	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Buttons	Save, Back	Save, Back

Figure 19. Example input forms for registering a device (like a GNSS tracker) in the system, and assigning it to a vehicle asset

3.2 SPATRA railway monitoring and prediction of rail temperature zones and early warnings pilot system definition and operational context

3.2.1 RWP service architecture

Figure 20. High-level architecture of SPATRA RWP service

As illustrated in Figure 20 above, the high-level architecture of the RWP Service comprises several interconnected components:

At the forefront is the **API Gateway**, serving as the central communication gateway between users and the RWP Service. It ensures unified access to all service functionalities.

The **Presentation and API** components provides user interfaces, primarily offering a web-based graphical interface via the WebGUI. These interfaces allow users to manage and visualize RTBR tasks, associated data and time series results, user-specific vector data, and notifications.

Job Management and Message Brokering collect and distribute derived jobs efficiently across the system, coordinating task execution among components.

Processor components play the main role for generating the RTT and RTBR data. This encompasses data discovery, collection, and harmonization from the data sources. They also generate downsampled thermal data, predict rail track temperatures, assess buckling risks, check for RTT thresholds exceedances and monitor data quality for anomalies.

Data Repository serves as the central repository, consisting of an Object Storage for unstructured data, SQL database for structured data including RTBR tasks and metadata.

Orthogonal components handle more generic but critical aspects such as identity management, caching, logging, and metric monitoring, ensuring system reliability and performance optimization.

3.2.2 RWP service components description and specification

3.2.2.1. Hardware components

In order to get data for RWP service development and pilot functioning, as well as for pilot validation, certain hardware components were selected to satisfy system requirements. The schematics of hardware components connection is given in Figure 21. Two in-situ measuring stations are formed which consist of set of sensors that measure rail temperature, rail displacement and meteorological/climate data. The sensors are powered by acquisition devices (marked with TA, DA, WA in Figure 21) which also acquire data from the sensors. All acquisition devices have an internal battery which is charged via the solar panel SP. The acquisition devices transmit measurement data over the Wi-Fi network to the wireless gateway (WG in Figure 21) which is also powered by an internal battery which is charged by the solar panel. The wireless gateway transmit data via the 4G modem to the processors of the RWP SPATRA service.

Figure 21. Schematics of sensor connection for the SPATRA RWP service

Weather station

Based on the analysis and requirements related to weather station presented in previous sections (SR-014, SR-043) and the high-level architecture of SPATRA RWP service (Figure 20), the weather station selected for the SPATRA RWP is Rika Sensors RK900-10 Ultrasonic Automatic Weather Instrument (Figure 22). RK900-10 Ultrasonic Automatic Weather Instrument simultaneously measures the atmospheric temperature, atmospheric humidity, air pressure, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, Illuminance/UV, dust concentration and precipitation. The main features of the SPATRA RWP weather station are given in Table 8.

Figure 22. Rika Sensors RK900-10 Ultrasonic Automatic Weather Instrument²²

Table 8 - The main features of SPATRA RWP weather station

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
Measure item			
Data	Wind speed	Principle: Ultrasonic, Range: 0 m/s to 60 m/s, Resolution: 0.01 m/s, Accuracy: $\pm 2\%$	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Wind direction	Principle: Ultrasonic, Range: 0° to 360°, Resolution: 1°, Accuracy: $\pm 3^\circ$	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Atmospheric temperature	Principle: MEMS, Range: -40° C to +80° C, Resolution: 0.1° C, Accuracy: $\pm 1^\circ$ C	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Atmospheric humidity	Principle: MEMS, Range: 0% to 100% RH, Resolution: 0.1% RH, Accuracy: $\pm 3\%$	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017

²² <https://www.rikasensor.com>, accessed on 26.06.2024

	Atmospheric pressure	Principle: MEMS, Range: 150 hPa to 1100 hPa, Resolution: 0.1 hPa, Accuracy: ± 1 hPa	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Precipitation (Rain/Hail/Snow)	Principle: Radar, Range: 0 mm/hr to 200 mm/hr, Resolution: 0.1 mm/hr, Accuracy: $\pm 5\%$ (@ wind speed ≤ 5 m/s)	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Solar radiation	Principle: Silicon-cell, Range: 0 W/m ² to 2000 W/m ² , Resolution: 0.1 W/m ² , Accuracy: $\pm 5\%$ (@ Vertical irradiation)	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Illuminance	Principle: Silicon-cell, Range: 0 lux to 200000 lux, Resolution: 0.1 lux, Accuracy: $\pm 5\%$ (@ Vertical irradiation)	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	UV	Principle: Silicon-cell, Range: 0 W/m ² to 2000 W/m ² , Resolution: 0.1 W/m ² , Accuracy: $\pm 10\%$	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Dust concentration (PM2.5, PM10)	Principle: Photoelectric scattering, Range: 0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 2000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Resolution: 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Accuracy: $\pm 10\%$	SR-007 SR-014 SR-017
	Visibility	Principle: Optical, Range: 10 m to 5000 m, Resolution: 1 m, Accuracy: $\pm 15\%$	SR-007 SR-014
General			
Data	Supply	12 to 24 VDC	-
	Output	RS485, RS232, SDI-12	SR-007 SR-014
	Communication Protocol	Modbus-rtu (default), NMEA-0183, SDI-12	SR-007 SR-014

Data update cycle	1s (default), other optional	SR-007 SR-014
Power consumption	< 5 W, auto-heating power: 9 W	-
Operating temperature	-40° C to +80° C	SR-007 SR-014
EMC	EN61000-6-3, EN61000-3-3 EN61000-3-2, EN61000-6-1	-
IP Rating	IP66	-
Main material	ASA, Aluminum alloy base (optional)	-

Rail temperature and displacement measurement system

Based on the analysis and requirements related to weather station presented in previous sections (SR-014, SR-043) and the high-level architecture of SPATRA RWP service (Figure 20), the in-situ rail temperature and displacement sensors selected for the SPATRA RWP are BeanDevice 2.4GHz ONE-T Wireless Industrial IOT Temperature Sensor (BND-2.4GHZ-ONE-T-ST), Magnetic Temperature Sensor PT1000 (013-L5-LG5-PT1000A-2L-3.0), and BeanAir displacement sensor DISP-SENS-SR-MS-100MM-CL-1M. Furthermore, the connectivity and power supply devices are also selected as shown on Figure 21. The main features of the SPATRA RWP in-situ rail temperature and displacement measurement system are given in Table 10 to Table 16.

Figure 23. BeanDevice 2.4GHz ONE-T Wireless Industrial IOT Temperature Sensor (BND-2.4GHZ-ONE-T-ST)²³

²³ <https://www.beanair.com>, accessed on 26.06.2024

Table 9 - The main features of SPATRA RWP temperature sensor

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
Temperature sensor specifications			
Data	Temperature Sensor technology	Silicon temperature probe, Probe watertightness: IP67, Mechanical assembly type: steel tube	SR-014 SR-017 SR-020
	Measurement range	-25° C to +75° C	SR-017 SR-020
	Measurement accuracy	±0.3° C between -10° C and +60° C	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Sensor resolution	0.1° C	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Sensor accuracy	Standard accuracy	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
RF Specifications			
Data	Wireless Technology	Ultra-Power and license-free 2.4 Ghz radio technology (IEEE 802.15.4E)	SR-007 SR-014
	WSN Topology	Point-to-Point / Star	SR-007 SR-014
	Data rate	250 Kbits/s	SR-007 SR-014
	RF Characteristics	ISM 2.4 GHz – 16 Channels	-

	TX Power	+18 dBm	-
	Receiver Sensitivity	-95,5 dBm to -104 dBm	-
	Maximum Radio Range	300 m (Line of Sight), 30 m to 80m (Non Line of Sight)	SR-007 SR-014
	Antenna	Omnidirectional antenna 2.2 dBi	-
Over-the-air configuration (OTAC) parameters			
Data	Alarm Threshold	3 thresholds of Alarms Alert < Action < Alarm	SR-009
	Data Acquisition mode	Low Duty Cycle Data Acquisition (LDCDA) Mode: 1 s to 24 hour Alarm mode: 1 s to 24 hour	SR-009 SR-014
	Power Mode	Battery saver mode	-
Embedded Data logger			
Data	Storage Capacity	up to 1000000 data points	SR-014 SR-033
	Wireless data downloading	3 minutes to download the full memory (average time)	SR-014 SR-033
Environmental and Mechanical			
Data	Casing	Polycarbonate, Waterproof IP67 – Fire Protection: ULV94 Casing dimensions (L x W x H): 110 mm x 36 mm x 34 mm Weight (battery included): 120 g	-
	Operating Temperature	-40° C to +75° C (data acquisition and A7 wireless transmission box)	SR-017 SR-018 SR-020
	Norms	FCC & CE compliant	-

		ROHS - Directive 2002/95/EC	
Power supply			
Data	Included primary cell	Lithium-thionyl chloride battery with 2200 mAh capacity (AA size)	-
	Current consumption @ 3.3 V	During data acquisition: 20 mA to 30 mA During Radio transmission: 60 mA During sleeping: < 10 μ A	-
Options			
Data	Calibration	DAkKS connected calibration	SR-043

Figure 24. BeanDevice 2.4GHz AN-mV Wireless IOT Data Acquisition Instrument (BND-2.4GHZ-AN-MV-4CH)²⁴

Table 10 - The main features of SPATRA RWP Wireless Data Acquisition Instrument

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
Analog data acquisition block specifications			

²⁴ <https://www.beanair.com>, accessed on 26.06.2024

Data	Signal Conditioning	Analog low voltage mV	SR-017 SR-020
	Number of channels	4 Channels	SR-017 SR-020
	A/D Converter	16 bits - SAR Architecture (Successive Approximation Register) with temperature compensation	SR-017 SR-020
	Measurement range	± 20 mV (bipolar) or 0 mV to 40 mV (unipolar)	SR-017 SR-020
	Non-linearity error	$\pm 0,5$ LSB	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Repeatability (full scale, @ 25° C, Static Measurement Mode every 2 s)	less than $\pm 0.025\%$	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Repeatability (full scale, @ 25° C, Dynamic Measurement Mode 10 Hz)	less than $\pm 0.35\%$	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Sensor Connector	M12 – 4 Pins, A-Coding, Waterproof IP67	-
Sensor Power Supply specifications			
Data	Power Supply	4.5 Volts to 20 Volts, dynamically configurable from the BeanScape 2.4GHz	-
	Power Supply precision (full scale, @ 25° C)	$\pm 0.18\%$	-
	Maximum Output Power (@ 25° C)	1 Watts	-

Configurable settings from the BeanScape 2.4GHz software			
Data	Data Acquisition mode	Static Data Acquisition: Low Duty Cycle Data Acquisition (LDCDA) and Survey (based on alarm thresholds) Mode. Measurement hearTBReat 1 s to 24 hours. Dynamic data acquisition (not available on devices with ref. extension XT): Streaming and S.E.T. (Streaming with Event Trigger) Mode	SR-007 SR-014
	Sampling Rate (SPS = sample per second)	Minimum: 1 SPS Maximum: 400 SPS maximum per channel	SR-007 SR-014
	Alarm Threshold	3 levels of Alarm Threshold Alert-Action-Alarm	SR-009
	Sensor power supply	4.5 Volts to 20 Volts	-
	Analog Input polarity	Bipolar or Unipolar	-
	Power Mode	Battery saver mode & Active power mode	-
TimeSync function: Clock synchronization over the Wireless IIOT Sensors			
Data	Clock synchronization accuracy	± 2.5 ms (at 25° C)	SR-014
	Crystal specifications	Tolerance ± 10 ppm, stability ± 10 ppm	SR-014
RF Specifications			
Data	Wireless Protocol Stack	Ultra-Power and license-free 2.4 GHz radio technology (IEEE 802.15.4E)	SR-007 SR-014
	WSN Topology	Point-to-Point / Star	SR-007 SR-014
	Data rate	250 Kbits/s	SR-007

			SR-014
	RF Characteristics	ISM 2.4 GHz – 16 Channels	SR-007 SR-014
	TX Power	+18 dBm	-
	Receiver Sensitivity	-104 dBm	-
	Maximum Radio Range	650 m (Line of Sight), 30 m to 100m (Non Line of Sight)	SR-007 SR-014
	Antenna diversity	2 omnidirectional N-Type antenna Gain: 5.5 dBi Waterproof IP67	-
Embedded Data logger			
Data	Storage Capacity	Up to 1 million data points	SR-033
	Wireless data downloading	3 minutes to download the full memory (average time)	SR-033
Environmental and Mechanical			
Data	Casing	Aluminum, Waterproof IP67 – Fire Protection: ULV94/Getex Casing dimensions (w/o antenna w eyelets) L x W x H: 125 mm x 82 mm x 57 mm Weight: 760 g	-
	Operating Temperature	-40° C to +60° C	SR-017 SR-018 SR-020
	Norms	CE Labelling Directive R&TTE (Radio) ETSI EN 300 328 FCC (North America)	-

		ARIB STD-T66 Ver 3.6 ROHS - Directive 2002/95/EC	
	Shocks resistance	50 g during 50 ms	-
Power supply			
Data	Integrated battery charger	Integrated Lithium-ion battery charger with high precision battery monitoring: Overvoltage Protection, Overcurrent / Short-Circuit Protection, Undervoltage Protection Battery Temperature monitoring	-
	Current consumption @ 3.3 V	During data acquisition: 70 mA to 130 mA (depends on external sensor power supply) During radio transmission: 70 mA During sleeping: < 35 μ A	-
	External power supply	+8-28 VDC with polarity inversion protection	-
	Rechargeable battery	High density Lithium-Ion rechargeable battery with a capacity of 2.2 Ah with polyswitch protection	-

Figure 25. BeanDevice 2.4 GHz AN-420 Wireless IOT Data Acquisition Instrument (BND-2.4GHZ-AN420-4CH)²⁵

²⁵ <https://www.beanair.com>, accessed on 26.06.2024

Table 11 - The main features of SPATRA RWP Wireless Data Acquisition Instrument

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
Analog data acquisition specifications			
Data	Signal Conditioning	Analog current loop measurement	SR-018
	Number of channels	4 Channels	SR-018
	A/D Converter	16 bits – SAR Architecture (Successive Approximation Register) with temperature compensation	SR-018
	Measurement range	4 mA to 20 mA Current Loop measurement	SR-018
	Non-linearity error	±0.5 LSB	SR-018
	Repeatability (full scale, @ 25° C, static Measurement Mode every 2 s)	less than ±0.01%	SR-018
	Repeatability (full scale, @ 25° C, Dynamic Measurement Mode 10 Hz)	less than ±0.01%	SR-018
	Sensor Connector	M12 – 4 Pins, A-Coding, Waterproof IP67	-
Sensor power supply specifications			
Data	Power Supply	4.5 Volts to 20 Volts, configurable from the BeanScape 2.4GHz software	-
	Power Supply precision (full scale, @ 25° C)	±0.18%	-

	Maximum Output Power (@ 25° C)	1 Watts	-
Configurable settings from the BeanScope 2.4GHz software			
Data	Data Acquisition mode	Static Data Acquisition: Low Duty Cycle Data Acquisition (LDCDA) and Alarm Mode (based on alarm thresholds). Measurement heartbeat 1 s to 24 hours. Dynamic data acquisition (not available on devices with ref. extension XT): Streaming and S.E.T. (Streaming with Event Trigger) Mode.	SR-007 SR-014
	Sampling Rate (SPS = samples per second)	Minimum: 1 SPS Maximum: 400 SPS maximum per channel	SR-007 SR-014
	Alarm Threshold	3 levels of Alarm Threshold Alert-Action-Alarm	SR-009
	Sensor power supply	4.5 Volts to 20 Volts	-
	Power Mode	Battery saver mode & Active power mode	-
Embedded data logger			
Data	Storage capacity	up to 1 million data points	SR-033
	Wireless data downloading	3 minutes to download the full memory (average time)	SR-033
RF specifications			
Data	Wireless Protocol Stack	Ultra-Power and license-free 2.4 GHz radio technology (IEEE 802.15.4E)	SR-007 SR-014
	WSN Topology	Point-to-Point / Star	SR-007 SR-014
	Data rate	250 Kbits/s	SR-007 SR-014

	RF Characteristics	ISM 2.4 GHz – 16 Channels	SR-007 SR-014
	TX Power	+18 dBm	-
	Receiver Sensitivity	-104 dBm	-
	Maximum Radio Range (In Transmission Mode)	650 m (Line of Sight), 30m to 100m (Non Line of Sight)	SR-007 SR-014
	Antenna diversity	2 omnidirectional N-Type antenna Gain: 5.5 dBi Waterproof IP67	-
TimeSync function: Clock synchronization over the Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN)			
Data	Clock synchronization accuracy	± 2.5 ms (at 25° C)	SR-014
	Crystal specifications	Tolerance ± 10 ppm, stability ± 10 ppm	SR-014
Environmental and mechanical			
Data	Casing	Aluminum, Waterproof IP67 – Fire Protection: ULV94/Getex Casing dimensions (w/o antenna, w eyelets) L x W x H: 156 mm x 82 mm x 57 mm Weight: 760 g	-
	Shocks resistance	50 g during 50 ms	-
	Operating Temperature	-40° C to +60° C	
	Norms	CE Labelling Directive R&TTE (Radio) ETSI EN 300 328 FCC (North America) ARIB STD-T66 Ver 3.6	-

		ROHS - Directive 2002/95/EC	
Power supply			
Data	Integrated battery charger	Integrated Lithium-ion battery charger with high precision battery monitoring: Overvoltage Protection, Overcurrent / Short-Circuit Protection, Undervoltage Protection Battery Temperature monitoring	-
	Current consumption @ 3.3 V	During data acquisition: 70 mA to 130 mA (depends on external sensor power supply) During Radio transmission: 70 mA During Battery Saver Mode: < 35 µA	-
	External power supply	+8-28 VDC with polarity inversion protection	-
	Rechargeable battery	High density Lithium-Ion rechargeable battery with a capacity of 2.2 Ah with polyswitch protection	-

Table 12 - The main features of SPATRA RWP real time Wireless IOT Sensors supervision and control monitor server (BeanScope 2.4GHz Basic)

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
General			
Data	Number of managed BeanDevice 2.4GHz	35	SR-033
	Real-time graph display	Yes	SR-007 SR-033
	Alarm notification by email: System and Data Acquisition alarms	Yes	SR-009 SR-025 SR-033

Streaming with Event-Trigger (S.E.T.) mode	Yes	SR-014 SR-033
NTP client	Yes	SR-014 SR-033
Automatic Reports (Waveform, FFT, PPV, Velocity)	Only Waveform report	SR-007 SR-014 SR-033
Free updates	1 year	-
Number of handled wireless sensor networks	1	SR-033
Delivery	FTP Access	-

Figure 26. BeanGateway Outdoor with 3G/4G/LTE connectivity, Power supplied from solar panel (BGTW-2.4GHZ-4G-SOLAR-OUT)²⁶

Table 13 - The main features of SPATRA RWP outdoor gateway with 3G/4G/LTE connectivity and solar power supply

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
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²⁶ <https://www.beanair.com>, accessed on 26.06.2024

Wireless IIOT Sensors Coordinator			
Data	Wireless Technology	Ultra-Power and license-free 2.4 GHz radio technology (IEEE 802.15.4E)	SR-007 SR-014 SR-041
	WSN Topology	Peer-to-peer / Star	SR-007 SR-014 SR-041
	Raw data rate	250 Kbits/s	SR-007 SR-014
	RF Characteristics	ISM 2.4 GHz – 16 Channels	SR-007 SR-014
	RF Transmit power	+18 dBm	-
	Receiver sensitivity	-104 dBm	-
	Maximum Radio Range	1 km (Line of Sight), 70 m to 150 m (Non Line of Sight)	SR-007 SR-014 SR-041
	WSN Diagnostic tool	Energy Scan for choosing a suitable RF Channel BeanDevice PER (Packet Error Rate) calculation LQI (Link Quality Indicator) between the BeanGateway and the BeanDevice RF channels Blacklist	SR-041
3G/4G Connectivity specifications			
Data	LTE	LTE FDD: B1/B3/B5/B7/B8/B20 LTE TDD: B38/B40/B41 LTE CAT4 up to 70 Mbps DL LTE CAT4 up to 50 Mbps UL	SR-007 SR-014

		Class 3 (23 dBm \pm 2 dB) for LTE FDD Class 3 (23 dBm \pm 2 dB) for LTE TDD	
	UMTS/DC-HSPA+	850/900/2100 MHz DC-HSPA+ mode: Max 42 Mbps (DL) Max 5.76 Mbps (UL) UMTS mode: 384 kbps DL, 384 kbps UL TD-SCDMA: Max 4.2 Mbps (DL) Max 2.2 Mbps (UL) Power Class 3 (24 dBm +1/-3 dB) for UMTS bands Class 3 (24 dBm +1/-3 dB) for TD-SCDMA	SR-007 SR-014
	GSM/GPRS/EDGE	900/1800 Mhz GPRS/EDGE Multi-slot Class 12 Power Class E2 (27 dBm \pm 3 dB) for GSM 900 Power Class E2 (26 dBm +3/-4 dB) for DCS 1800 Power Class 4 (33 dBm \pm 2 dB) for GSM 900 Power Class 1 (30 dBm \pm 2 dB) for DCS 1800	SR-007 SR-014
	Omnidirectional 4G Antenna	Omnidirectional 4G Antenna (2x2 MIMO) Weather-resistant and UV-resistant plastic / PVC enclosure VSWR < 1.8 Impedance: 50 Ohm Beamwidth: 360° Horizontal – 20° Vertical Gain: 8 dBi @ 800 MHz 12 dBi @ 1800 MHz 12 dBi @ 2600 MHz Frequency: 791 MHz to 862 MHz (2G, 4G) 1700 MHz to 2100 MHz (3G, 4G)	SR-007 SR-014

		2500 MHz to 2700 MHz (4G) Connectors: 2 x N female Mounting Kit: U-clamp for 30 mm to 50 mm diameter handles	
Physical & Environmental			
Data	Casing	Steel enclosure with padlock adapter, Light gray color	-
	Dimensions	25.4 cm x 20.3 cm x 15.24 cm	-
	IP NEMA Rating	IP66 Nema 6	-
	Weight	9.3 kg	-
	Mounting Process	Screw mounting	-
	Operating Temperature	Battery Charging: -15° C to 50° C Battery Discharging: -20° C to 60° C	-
	Norms & Radio Certifications	CE Labelling Directive R&TTE (Radio) ETSI EN 300 328 (Europe) FCC Part 15.247 (North America) IC RS210 ROHS - Directive 2002/95/EC	-
Solar Panel power supply with UPS Battery (Ref: BGTW-4G-SOLAR-OUT)			
Data	Battery	Valve Regulated Lead-Acid (VRLA) Capacity 12 Ah	-
	Solar panel technology	Monocrystalline 100 W, anodized aluminum frame Surface protection with ESG solarglass Dimensions (L x W x H): 100 mm x 77.5 mm x 25 mm	-
	Solar charging controller	Maximum Input current: 6 A	-

		Power consumption < 2.5 mA, Led switch on Nominal voltage: 12 VDC Led displays: battery full and charging	
	Socket for Solar Panel Connection	Industrial and Waterproof Socket Circular Socket CA 3 GD – Hirschmann Rated Voltage: 400 VA Rated Current: 16 A	-
Included accessories			
Data	4G Antenna	1 x 4G Antenna 12 dBi - with pole mounting Ref: WL-4G-HG-ANT-12DBI	SR-014
	WIFI Antenna	1 x High Gain Wifi Antenna 9 dBi - with pole mounting kit Ref: HG-OMNI-OUT-7DBI	SR-014
	External cable for WIFI Antenna	1 x N-Type cable, Cable Length: 2 meters Ref: CBL-ANT-1M	-
	External cable for LTE Antenna	2 x N-Type cable, Cable Length: 2 meters Ref: CBL-ANT-1M	-

Figure 27. BeanAir Displacement sensor with integrated spring return (DISP-SENS-SR-MS-100MM-CL-1M)²⁷

Table 14 - The main features of SPATRA RWP Displacement sensor with integrated spring return

²⁷ <https://www.beanair.com>, accessed on 26.06.2024

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
General			
Data	Sensor technology	Linear potentiometer with spring return	SR-018 SR-019
	Measurement stroke	100 mm	SR-018 SR-019
	Linearity	±0.2%	SR-018 SR-019
	Repeatability	< 0.01 mm	SR-018 SR-019
	Resolution	Related to BeanDevice AN-V precision, 0.01%	SR-018 SR-019
	Resistance	5 kOhm	-
	Max Voltage	28 VDC. Can be directly powered from BeanDevice AN-V, recommended power voltage 5 VDC (BeanDevice AN-V ±5 V) or 10 VDC (BeanDevice AN-V ±10 V)	-
	Displacement speed	< 5 m/s	-
	Mechanical Life	100 million movements	-
	Casing dimensions	18 mm of diameter	-
	Casing material	Anodized Aluminum	-
	Rod material	Stainless steel	-
	Rod diameter	5 mm of diameter	-
Mechanical mounting	Variable brackets	-	

	Waterproofness	IP66	-
	Operating Temperature	-20° C to +80° C	SR-018 SR-019
	Connection Plug	M12 – 4 pins Plug Waterproof IP67	-
	BeanDevice Compatibility	Compatible with BeanDevice 2.4GHz AN-V ± 5 V and ± 10 V	SR-014

Figure 28. BeanDevice AN-V wireless IOT data acquisition instrument with analog voltage input ± 10 V (BND-2.4GHZ-ANV-10-4CH)²⁸

Table 15 - The main features of SPATRA RWP wireless IOT data acquisition instrument with analog voltage input

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
Analog data acquisition specifications			

²⁸ <https://www.beanair.com>, accessed on 27.06.2024

Data	Signal Conditioning	Analog voltage measurement	SR-018 SR-019
	Number of channels	4 Channels	SR-018 SR-019
	A/D Converter	16 bits – SAR Architecture (Successive Approximation Register) with temperature compensation	SR-018 SR-019
	Measurement range (analog polarity is dynamically configurable from the BeanScape 2.4GHz)	± 10 V (bipolar) or 0 V to 20 V (unipolar)	SR-018 SR-019
	Repeatability (full scale, @ 25° C, Static Measurement Mode every 2 s)	less than $\pm 0.01\%$	SR-018 SR-019
	Repeatability (full scale, @ 25° C, Dynamic Measurement Mode 10 Hz)	less than $\pm 0.01\%$	SR-018 SR-019
	Non-linearity error	± 5 LSB	SR-018 SR-019
	Sensor Connector	M12 – 4 Pins, A-Coding, Waterproof IP67	-
Sensor Power Supply specifications			
Data	Power Supply	4.5 Volts to 20 Volts, dynamically configurable from the BeanScape 2.4GHz	-
	Power Supply precision (full scale, @ 25° C)	$\pm 0.18\%$	-

	Maximum Output Power (@ 25° C)	1 Watts	-
Configurable settings from the BeanScope 2.4GHz software			
Data	Data Acquisition mode	Static Data Acquisition: Low Duty Cycle Data Acquisition (LDCDA) and Survey (based on alarm thresholds) Mode. Measurement hearTBReat 1 s to 24 hour. Dynamic data acquisition (not available on devices with ref. extension XT): Streaming and S.E.T. (Streaming with Event Trigger) Mode	SR-007 SR-014
	Sampling Rate (SPS = sample per second)	Minimum: 1 SPS Maximum: 400 SPS maximum per channel	SR-007 SR-014
	Alarm Threshold	3 levels of Alarm Threshold Alert-Action-Alarm	SR-009
	Sensor power supply	4.5 Volts to 20 Volts	-
	Analog Input polarity	Bipolar or Unipolar	-
	Power Mode	Battery saver mode & Active power mode	-
TimeSync function: Clock synchronization over the Wireless IIOT Sensors			
Data	Clock synchronization accuracy	± 2.5 ms (at 25° C)	SR-014
	Crystal specifications	Tolerance ± 10 ppm, stability ± 10 ppm	SR-014
RF Specifications			
Data	Wireless Protocol Stack	Ultra-Power and license-free 2.4 GHz radio technology (IEEE 802.15.4E)	SR-007 SR-014
	WSN Topology	Point-to-Point / Star	SR-007 SR-014

	Data rate	250 Kbits/s	SR-007 SR-014
	RF Characteristics	ISM 2.4 GHz – 16 Channels	SR-007 SR-014
	TX Power	+18 dBm	-
	Receiver Sensitivity	-104 dBm	-
	Maximum Radio Range	650 m (Line of Sight), 30 m to 100 m (Non Line of Sight)	SR-007 SR-014
	Antenna diversity	2 omnidirectional N-Type antenna Gain: 5.5 dBi Waterproof IP67	-
Embedded Data logger			
Data	Storage Capacity	Up to 1 million data points	SR-033
	Wireless data downloading	3 minutes to download the full memory (average time)	SR-033
Environmental and Mechanical			
Data	Casing	Aluminum, Waterproof IP67 – Fire Protection: ULV94/Getex Casing dimensions (w/o antenna, w eyelets) L x W x H: 125 mm x 82 mm x 57 mm Weight: 760 g	-
	Operating Temperature	-40° C to +60° C	SR-018 SR-019
	Norms	CE Labelling Directive R&TTE (Radio) ETSI EN 300 328	-

		FCC (North America) ARIB STD-T66 Ver 3.6 ROHS - Directive 2002/95/EC	
	Shocks resistance	50 g during 50 ms	-
Power supply			
Data	Integrated battery charger	Integrated Lithium-ion battery charger with high precision battery monitoring: Overvoltage Protection, Overcurrent / Short-Circuit Protection, Undervoltage Protection Battery Temperature monitoring	-
	Current consumption @ 3.3 V	During data acquisition: 70 mA to 130 mA (depends on external sensor power supply) During Radio transmission: 70 mA During sleeping: < 35 μ A	-
	External power supply	+8-28 VDC with polarity inversion protection	-
	Rechargeable battery	High density Lithium-Ion rechargeable battery with a capacity of 2.2 Ah with polyswitch protection	-

Table 16 - The main features of SPATRA RWP Magnetic Temperature Sensor PT1000 (013-L5-LG5-PT1000A-2L-3.0)

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
General			
Data	Cable material	Glass fiber	-
	Sensor	PT1000	SR-017

	Sensor class	CLASS A	SR-017
	Design Temperature (Standard)	-50° C to +250° C	SR-017
	Circuit type	2 conductors	-

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

Based on the requirements for achieving the RWP accuracy (SR-047), the UAV selected for the SPATRA RWP is DJI Matrice 30T (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**Figure 29), with thermal imaging camera as the main sensor component for collecting validation data. The main features of the SPATRA RWP UAV are given in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The UAV is used only for the validation in pilot demonstration, and it is not a part of SPATRA RWP service.

Figure 29. DJI Matrice 30T UAV²⁹

Table 17 - The main features of SPATRA RWP UAV

Type	Feature	Value	System Req.
Aircraft			

²⁹ www.dji.com, accessed on 26.06.2024

Data	Dimensions (unfolded, excl. propellers)	470 mm × 585 mm × 215 mm (L × W × H)	-
	Dimensions (folded)	365 mm × 215 mm × 195 mm (L × W × H)	-
	Diagonal Wheelbase	668 mm	-
	Weight (incl. two batteries)	3770 ± 10 g	-
	Max Take-off Weight	4069 g	-
	Max Take-off Weight for C2 Certification in EU	3998 g	-
	Operation Frequency	2.4000 GHz to 2.4835 GHz (Europe)	-
	Transmitter Power (EIRP)	2.4 GHz CE (Europe): < 20 dBm	-
	Hovering Accuracy (windless or breezy)	Vertical: ±0.1 m (Vision System enabled); ±0.5 m (N-mode with GPS); ±0.1 m (RTK) Horizontal: ±0.3 m (Vision System enabled); ±1.5 m (N-mode with GPS); ±0.1 m (RTK)	-
	RTK Positioning Accuracy (fixed RTK enabled)	1 cm + 1 ppm (horizontal) 1.5 cm + 1 ppm (vertical)	SR-014 SR-017 SR-018 SR-020
	Max Angular Velocity	Pitch: 150°/sec.; Yaw: 100°/sec.	-
	Max Pitch Angle	35° (N-mode and Forward Vision System enabled: 25°)	-
	Max Ascent/Descent Speed	6 m/s, 5 m/s	-
Max Tilt Descent Speed	7 m/s	-	

	Max Horizontal Speed	23 m/s	-
	Max Service Ceiling Above Sea Level (without other payload)	5000 m (with 1671 propellers)	-
	Max Wind Resistance	12 m/s	-
	Max Hover Time	36 min	-
	Max Flight Time	41 min	-
	Motor Model	3511	-
	Propeller Model	1671 1676 High Altitude (not included)	-
	Ingress Protection Rating	IP55	-
	GNSS	GPS + Galileo + BeiDou + GLONASS (GLONASS is supported only when RTK module is enabled)	-
	Operating Temperature	-20° C to 50° C	SR-017 SR-018 SR-020
Gimbal			
Data	Angular Vibration Range	±0.01°	-
	Controllable Range	Pan: ±90° Tilt: -120° to +45°	-
	Mechanical Range	Pan: ±105° Tilt: -135° to +60° Roll: ±45°	-
Thermal Camera			

Data	Thermal Imager	Uncooled VOx Microbolometer	SR-014 SR-017 SR-020
	Lens	DFOV: 61° Focal length: 9.1 mm (equivalent: 40 mm) Aperture: f/1.0 Focus: 5 m to ∞	SR-043
	Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference (NETD)	≤ 50 mK @ F1.0	SR-017 SR-020
	Infrared Temperature Measurement Accuracy	±2° C or ±2% (using the larger value)	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043 SR-045 SR-047
	Video Resolution	Infrared Image Super-resolution Mode: 1280 × 1024 Normal Mode: 640 × 512	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Photo Size	Infrared Image Super-resolution Mode: 1280 × 1024 Normal Mode: 640 × 512	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Pixel Pitch	12 μm	SR-017 SR-020 SR-043
	Temperature Measurement Method	Spot Meter, Area Measurement	SR-017 SR-020
	Temperature Measurement Range	High Gain Mode: -20° C to 150° C Low Gain Mode: 0° C to 500° C	SR-017 SR-020

			SR-043
	Temperature Alert	Supported	SR-014
	Palette	White Hot / Black Hot / Tint / Iron Red / Hot Iron / Arctic / Medical / Fulgurite / Rainbow 1 / Rainbow 2	SR-007
Vision Systems			
Data	Obstacle Sensing Range	Forward: 0.6 m to 38 m Upward/Downward/Backward/Sideward: 0.5 m to 33 m	-
	FOV	65° (H), 50° (V)	-
	Operating Environment	Surfaces with clear patterns and adequate lighting (> 15 lux)	-
Infrared Sensing Systems			
Data	Obstacle Sensing Range	0.1 m to 10 m	-
	FOV	30°	-
	Operating Environment	Large, diffuse, and reflective obstacles (reflectivity > 10%)	-
O3 Enterprise Transmission			
Data	Operating Frequency	2.4000 GHz to 2.4835 GHz (Europe)	-
	Max Transmission Distance (unobstructed, free of interference)	8 km CE (Europe)	SR-014
	Max Transmission Distance (with interference)	Strong Interference (urban landscape, limited line of sight, many competing signals): 1.5 km to 3 km CE (Europe) Medium Interference (suburban landscape, open line of sight, some competing signals): 3 km to 6 km CE (Europe)	SR-014

		Weak Interference (open landscape abundant line of sight, few competing signals): 6 km to 8 km CE (Europe)	
	Transmitter Power (EIRP)	2.4 GHz CE (Europe): < 20 dBm	-

3.2.2.2. Software components

This section provides a short insight into each software component, outlining its role, methodology, inputs and outputs where applicable. Further details on these components will be provided in the following deliverables of WP3.

API Gateway

The API Gateway acts as the central entry point for all client requests to the system's APIs. It is responsible for verifying client authentication and authorization, enforcing rate limiting, routing requests to appropriate services, load balancing, integrating with service discovery mechanisms, caching responses, validating and transforming input, and managing API versioning. This centralization ensures secure, efficient, and scalable access to backend services while simplifying client interactions with a unified endpoint (SR-001).

WebGUI

The WebGUI component serves as the primary user interface, offering a responsive web-based graphical interface accessible via standard browsers (Figure 30). It supports interactive maps with multiple switchable layers like Open Street Map, Open Railway Map, and satellite imagery, enhancing spatial data visualization and contextual understanding. (SR-002, SR-003)

Users can manage their vector data by uploading, browsing, selecting, downloading, deleting, and overlaying it on base maps, with GEOJSON format support. The WebGUI also facilitates RTBR task management, allowing users to perform CRUD operations and view associated metadata. (SR-005, SR-006)

Authentication is handled by redirecting users to the Identity Provider's login page, ensuring secure access. The interface includes features for data visualization, such as displaying RTBR subtask assets with configurable colormaps and contextual information like datetime and weather conditions. (SR-004, SR-007)

Users can aggregate and visualize time series data for multiple POIs and AOIs, choosing aggregation methods and target granularity, with options to download in formats like CSV, JSON, PDF, and PNG. Notification management is robust, providing pop-up alerts and customizable preferences for channels like RSS and email. (SR-008, SR-009)

Figure 30. Service mock-up showing rail track temperature predictions on a map (left) and hourly predictions as a temperature curve (right)

Figure 31. Service mock-up with buckling risk predictions on a map

The two figures, Figure 30 and Figure 31, illustrate a mock-up of the WebGUI for the RWP service. The first figure shows a track segment near Nis with its railway lines overlaid with Landsat 8 LST data at a 30m spatial resolution. The data, collected on August 14, 2023, at 9:15 am, provides a realistic representation of the rail track temperature (RTT) for the mock-up, targeting a resolution of 500m or less. Users can place markers on the rail tracks to display statistics, such as the temperature curve with predicted hourly temperatures shown on the right side of the interface. The second figure displays the rail tracks overlaid with buckling risk predictions. The risk of buckling is determined by comparing the critical rail temperature (CRT) with the RTT.

- **Green:** RTT is below the CRT, indicating a low risk of buckling.
- **Red:** RTT is above the CRT, indicating a high risk of buckling.
- **Orange:** Areas where the RTT is approaching the CRT, suggesting a potential risk of buckling.

Data Catalog API

The Data Catalog API is responsible for providing standardized access to geospatial data catalogs, managing RTBR tasks, and facilitating querying of metadata for finished RTBR subtasks. It implements a STAC API for interoperability and supports CRUD operations for RTBR tasks and user vector data. (SR-010)

Data Gateway

The Data Gateway serves as the single access point to the object storage for all CRUD operations. It manages data access, implements caching mechanisms, and provides a layer of abstraction between the system components and the underlying object storage. (SR-012)

Job Management

The Job Management is responsible for distributing jobs from the Job Management queue to the queues of the components responsible for job execution. It ensures efficient job coordination, supports horizontal and vertical scaling based on job resource consumption, allows modification of job parameters, prioritizes jobs based on specified criteria, provides real-time monitoring and reporting of job status, and supports the resumption of interrupted or failed jobs. (SR-011)

Data Sources

The RWP service will rely on a variety of data sources, including EO data such as Sentinel-3 LST or Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) LST, as well as in-situ measurements from sensors and drones. All EO and meteorological data products not already described in the hardware components are listed and are described in section 3.2.4

Data Discovery and Processor Job Generation

The Data Discovery and Processor Job Generation component is responsible for monitoring Data Sources for newly published data, generating RTBR subtasks and tile-subtasks from RTBR tasks, and creating STAC collection and item templates for RTBR tile-subtasks. It ensures timely discovery of new data and efficient organization of processing tasks. (SR-013, SR-014)

Data Collection and Harmonization

The Data Collection and Harmonization (DCH) continuously performs data discovery, collection, preprocessing and harmonisation for the data products required from data providers such as CDSE, Open-Meteo and in situ data. Where appropriate, only those parts of the data that intersect with the AOI will be downloaded. The preprocessing and harmonisation steps include operations such as mosaicking, cloud masking, clipping, reprojecting and calculation of indices such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and ensure that the data are ready for further processing. (SR-015, SR-016)

Outputs: The preprocessed data will be ingested into the Data Repository in common cloud native formats such as the cloud optimized GeoTIFF (COG) and Zarr (SR-060), and its metadata in the STAC format for efficient data cataloguing.

Thermal Downscaling

Role: The Thermal Downscaling component will improve the spatial resolution of the LST data from Sentinel-3, MODIS and MSG (provided by CLMS) through downscaling with data fusion technique. Thermal downscaling will combine coarse-resolution thermal data from various satellites (Sentinel-3, MODIS and MSG) with high-resolution surface characteristics from Sentinel-2 and other ancillary datasets. Based on machine learning approaches, this component will downscale LST data from resolutions such as 1km and 5km to the required resolution of 500m or finer (SR-017, SR-043). An example of the downscaling of the spatial resolution of Sentinel-3 LST data from 1km to 450m is shown in Figure 32.

Methodology: Kernel-based downscaling approaches with data fusion techniques will be employed to accomplish this. Kernel-based downscaling methods assume that the LST for subpixels in a main pixel can be derived from the LST of the main pixel itself and the surface characteristics (kernels) of the subpixels, including features such as vegetation, buildings and water bodies. In this context, the surface characteristics of the subpixels are represented by indices like NDVI, which are computed from Sentinel-2 MSI Level 2 bands. Additional possible sources for land surface characteristics include land surface covers provided by datasets like ESA World Cover data and digital elevation models such as in the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 data. (SR-017)

The Thermal Downscaling component may also implement downscaling approaches appropriate for historical time series data to improve time/resource performance and accuracy. (SR-017)

Inputs: The primary inputs consist of the pre-processed and harmonised Sentinel-3, Aqua/Terra MODIS and MSG LST data, together with several optical bands from Sentinel-2, which are used to calculate indices such as NDVI, which will be fused during the downscaling process.

Outputs: The generated downscaled LST data will be ingested into the Data Repository in COG and Zarr formats (SR-060), accompanied by metadata in the STAC format.

Figure 32. Improvement of the spatial resolution of Sentinel-3 LST data from 1km to 450m (Date: 14th August 2023 at 9:20am, Region: Nis, Serbia)

Rail Track Temperature Prediction

Role: The Rail Track Temperature Prediction (RTTP) predicts the RTT at the target resolution of 500m or finer (SR-043) for a 24-hour forecast window (SR-021)(SR-018). For RTT prediction, the component fuses downscaled LST data with in-situ RTT measurements, historical and forecast meteorological variables, and solar radiation data. This multi-source integration enables the machine learning model to accurately capture the interactions between environmental factors and track temperature.

Inputs: The RTTP relies on a variety of input data sources to provide accurate RTT predictions. These include downscaled LST data, generated by the Thermal Downscaling component, from which the temperatures of the rail areas are extracted, as shown in Figure 33 for example, and RTT measurements collected from in situ stations. Furthermore, historical, current and forecasted meteorological variables such as air temperature, precipitation, wind speed, cloud cover and relative humidity comprises crucial input data. Finally, solar effects such as total solar irradiance, azimuth and altitude are added to account for the influence of solar radiation on the temperature dynamics of the tracks.

Outputs: The predicted RTT data will be stored in COG and Zarr formats (SR-060), accompanied by metadata in the STAC format.

Methodology: A machine learning model will be trained on in situ RTT measurements to predict RTT using downscaled LST data, weather conditions and solar effects. On the one hand, to ensure a spatial resolution of 500m or finer (SR-043), downscaled LST data will be included as a machine learning feature, with all data spatially co-registered to match the format of the downscaled data. On the other hand, to meet the requirement of forecasting hourly RTT within a 24-hour window (SR-021), weather forecasts from ECMWF are leveraged (SR-018).

This component uses data fusion techniques to combine different data sources, including downscaled LST data, in-situ RTT measurements and weather forecasts, to produce high-resolution RTT forecasts. The integration of these different data inputs improves the accuracy and spatial resolution of the RTT forecasts.

Figure 33. Extraction of rail tracks from downscaled Sentinel-3 LST images for RTT predictions.

Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment

Role: The Rail Track Buckling Risk Assessment (RTBRA) assesses RTBR for different rail sites with different rail curvatures and environmental positions (sunny, shade, partial shade), over the entire rail network. (SR-019, SR-020)

Inputs: RTBRA relies on predicted RTT data to provide accurate RTBR assessments, as well as track curvature, track position regarding the environment, solar irradiation, track type, and track state.

Outputs: The RTBR assessments will be stored in COG and Zarr formats (SR-060), accompanied by metadata in the STAC format.

Methodology: Predicted RTT data will be used for RTBR assessments, considering critical rail temperatures available for different countries and rail curvatures. In addition, algorithm for RTBR assessment can incorporate site-specific risk factors, which are track and traffic specific, for more accurate assessment. A suitable model for the correlation of RTT and rail lateral displacement will be developed. Rail lateral displacement will be predicted by machine learning and provided to decision makers along with RTBR assessment. (SR-019, SR-020)

Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring

The Quality Control and Threshold Exceedance Monitoring component identifies when rail track temperature (RTT) exceeds predefined thresholds and scans critical data in the Data Repository for anomalies, assessing both incoming and internally generated data. This component ensures data reliability by evaluating quality metrics and detecting unusual patterns or outliers, supporting proactive maintenance and safety measures through early detection of critical conditions. (SR-023, SR-024, SR-025)

Notifications and Alerts

The Notifications and Alerts component analyzes metadata from completed RTBR subtasks to generate notifications. These notifications are displayed directly to users via the WebGUI and distributed through configured channels such as RSS feeds and email when applicable. The component ensures timely and secure delivery of critical information, employing secure transmission protocols, retry mechanisms for failed notifications, and maintaining high availability. (SR-026, SR-027)

Map Tiles API

The Map Tiles API is responsible for delivering images of raster data assets from the STAC catalogue as XYZ tiles. It provides a standardized method for accessing raster data as map tiles, ensuring compatibility with various mapping clients and supporting the visualization of RTBR and RTT data. (SR-028)

Time Series Analytics API

The Time Series Analytics API is designed to deliver data values for Points of Interest (POIs), aggregate time series data for specified Areas of Interest (AOIs) and POIs, and perform trend analysis on this aggregated data. It supports various statistical operations and levels of granularity for comprehensive data analysis. (SR-029, SR-030)

Identity Provider

The Identity Provider component is responsible for managing user authentication, authorization, and access control across the system. It implements a comprehensive Identity and Access Management solution, supporting user authentication (including username/password), role-based access control, and OAuth2/OpenID Connect protocols. The component provides user and group management interfaces, enforces configurable password policies, and maintains audit logs for all authentication and authorization events. It offers self-service account management features and APIs for integrating authentication and authorization into applications. (SR-031)

Cache Component

The Cache component is responsible for storing frequently accessed data to reduce access times and load on the primary data source. It implements data storage, retrieval, and management functionalities, including cache invalidation, expiration policies, and eviction strategies. It aims to improve system performance by efficiently managing frequently accessed data, supporting various caching strategies, and providing insights into cache usage and effectiveness. (SR-032)

Metric and Logging Monitoring

The Metrics and Logging Monitoring component is responsible for collecting metrics and logs from all monitored components, providing real-time monitoring, visualization, and alerting capabilities. It supports historical data analysis, custom dashboard creation, and flexible querying of collected data. It ensures comprehensive monitoring of the system, facilitating proactive issue detection, performance optimization, and efficient troubleshooting through centralized metrics and log management. (SR-033)

Message Brokering

The Message Brokering provides job queues for the Job Management and the processor components. It facilitates: Quick access to queued jobs, ensuring efficient job distribution and execution. Storage and prioritization of jobs based on specified criteria. Support for job resumption and management of interrupted or failed jobs. Centralized management of job queues to support system scalability and resource allocation. (SR-012)

Data Repository

The Data Repository component serves as a housing for all data generated by the system. It includes: The Object Storage for unstructured data like raster images (SR-011, SR-060) and the SQL Database for structured data such as metadata from the data catalog, tasks specifications and user vector data (SR-005, SR-006, SR-010, SR-014, SR-020)

3.2.3 RWP service interfaces

The primary service interface is a web-based graphical interface provided by the WebGUI component. For more details, see section API Gateway. When a user interacts with the WebGUI, their browser implicitly calls dedicated service REST API endpoints to execute the requests. (SR-002 - SR-009)

These service REST API endpoints can also be accessed independently of the WebGUI, allowing users to integrate the service backend into their internal systems and make bulk requests programmatically, such as registering RTBR tasks for multiple AOIs stored in a file. (SR-010, SR-028, SR-029, SR-030).

For authentication, users are redirected to the web-based graphical interface of the Identity Provider. (SR-004, SR-031)

Notifications and alerts for the user can be distributed via e-mail and RSS feed. (SR-027)

All user interfaces are routed through the API Gateway component to facilitate easier API management. (SR-001)

Finally, the service interfaces to the Data Sources are implemented directly in the processor components, which request data from the Data Sources as needed. (SR-013, SR-014, SR-015)

3.2.4 RWP service aggregation with EO data services and products

The RWP service will use a variety of EO data services and products to accurately and reliably predict track temperatures and assess buckling risk. By combining satellite data with in-situ measurements and weather/climate forecasts, the RWP service will provide comprehensive local monitoring and forecasting capabilities. This section describes the various EO data products used in this service.

Data Product	Data Provider	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Usage in RWP
Sentinel-3 LST Level 2	CDSE	1km	Twice per day Morning, evening	Input for LST downscaling algorithm

Sentinel-3, part of the Copernicus programme and provided by Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE)³⁰, monitors the oceans and land. It provides data such as LST, which is crucial for understanding RTT and environmental conditions. The planned RWP service will be based on high-resolution LST derived from Sentinel-3 LST data, downsampled from its spatial resolution of 1 km to 500m or finer (SR-043).

³⁰ <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>

Aqua/Terra MODIS LST Level 2	Earthdata ³¹	1km	Twice daily Aqua: night, midday Terra: morning, evening	Input for LST downscaling algorithm and validation
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The **Aqua and Terra satellites**, part of NASA's Earth Observing System (EOS), provide crucial LST data through the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) instruments. The MODIS LST Level 2 product offers a spatial resolution of 1 km and is available twice daily, with Aqua providing observations at night and midday, and Terra capturing data in the morning and evening. This temporal coverage ensures comprehensive monitoring of temperature variations throughout the day. The high-resolution MODIS LST data serve as a critical input for the LST downscaling algorithm, enabling the refinement of temperature predictions to a finer spatial resolution of 500m or less (SR-043). Additionally, MODIS LST data are used to validate the downscaled LST products, ensuring accuracy and reliability in the temperature predictions. Aqua's midday observations provide essential insights into temperature conditions during the hottest part of the day, addressing the limitation of Sentinel-3, which only captures data in the morning and evening. This complementary temporal coverage enhances the overall accuracy and reliability of the RTT monitoring.

MSG LST	CLMS	5km	Hourly	Input for LST downscaling algorithm
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The **geostationary MSG LST data** are provided by CLMS as Copernicus LST, which is a fused dataset product from multiple geostationary satellites. It provides a comprehensive set of environmental observations critical for RTT monitoring. With a spatial resolution of 5km and hourly updates, MSG observations provide crucial insights into short-term temperature variations along rail tracks. To complement the Sentinel-3 data and overcome temporal resolution limitations, hourly LST data from the MSG satellites, albeit at 5km spatial resolution, will be used for the proposed RTT monitoring over large areas (SR-021). In addition, MSG data can be downscaled from 5 km to the target resolution of 500m or finer to satisfy user needs (SR-043). Once Meteosat Third Generation (MTG) data are available, they will be able to replace MSG data, which have a spatial resolution of 2km.

Landsat 8/9 LST Level 2	CDSE	30m	8 days	Validation data for LST downscaling
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High-resolution LST EO data products, such as Landsat 8/9 LST Level 2, provided by CDSE with a spatial resolution of 30m (100m ground sample distance) and updated every 8 days, serve as validation data for the LST downscaling.

³¹ <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/>

Sentinel-2 MSI Level 2	CDSE	10m, 20m	5 days	Input data for LST downscaling algorithm
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Sentinel-2, part of the Copernicus programme and provided by CDSE, supplies high resolution optical images with multispectral data. From these bands indices such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) can be calculated, which are crucial for understanding the impact of vegetation on temperature variations in railways. These data are used as machine learning features for the LST downscaling.

Copernicus DEM GLO-30	CDSE	30m	n.a.	Input data for LST downscaling to improve prediction
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The **Copernicus DEM GLO-30**, provided by CDSE, provides a detailed view of the terrain with a spatial resolution of 30m. These digital elevation models serve as input data for LST downscaling to improve predictive capabilities, allowing terrain features to be incorporated into temperature prediction models.

ESA World Cover	CDSE	10m	Annually	Input data for LST downscaling to improve prediction
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The **ESA World Cover** dataset provided by CDSE contains a detailed representation of land cover with a spatial resolution of 10m. These detailed land cover products serve as input data for the LST downscaling algorithm to improve prediction capabilities.

ECMWF/ ERA5 Reanalysis	Open-Meteo ³²	25km	hourly	Input data for RTT forecasting
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Climate/Forecasted Weather data, such as the ECMWF/ERA5 reanalysis dataset accessible through Open-Meteo, provides hourly climate and weather data with a spatial resolution of 25 km. This comprehensive dataset integrates historical observations with advanced numerical weather models, providing detailed estimates of atmospheric, land and oceanic variables. This data is essential for machine learning models aimed at RTT forecasting. The high temporal resolution ensures accurate and timely weather insights, improving the reliability of RTT forecasts.

³² <https://open-meteo.com/>

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The document is the deliverable report D2.1 for the SPATRA project, which aims to enhance land transport monitoring and management through the development and implementation of two innovative applications, road and rail, based on satellite data. The road transport pilot (RDP) aims to address the problem of cross-border road congestion and parking availability, which cause significant economic losses and environmental impacts for the logistics sector. The RDP service will use EGNSS and Copernicus data, as well as UAVs and cameras, to monitor and predict traffic conditions and delays, and to provide alerts and recommendations to the users for route planning and optimization. The rail transport pilot (RWP) aims to address the problem of rail track deformation and buckling caused by high temperatures, which pose safety risks and reliability issues for the rail services. The RWP service will use Copernicus data, as well as weather data and in-situ sensors, to monitor and predict rail track temperature and buckling risk, and to provide notifications and early warnings to the users for preventive maintenance and operational decision-making.

This deliverable D2.1 report focuses on the requirements and specifications for two use-cases, road and rail transport, based on the inputs from the main stakeholders and end-users, logistic company Nelt and Serbian Railways Infrastructure. The report provides an overview of the methodologies and approaches adopted by the project consortium, as well as the key findings and future actions to achieve the project objectives. The report also defines the functional and non-functional requirements, system specifications (both hardware and software), data sources and processing steps, the preliminary system architectures and components, and the interfaces and integration roadmaps for the two use cases. In this way, this deliverable D2.1 reports on several initial stages of pilot deployments as illustrated in Figure 34. All illustrated stages of the process of pilots' deployments and roadmap to field-testing validation will be described in detail in deliverable D4.1- Pilot Plan and Protocol Specification.

Figure 34. High-level illustration of SPATRA pilots' implementation and roadmap for field-testing validation.